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Summary

Grouping of substances and read-across is an ‘alternative to animal testing’ approach for the safety assessment of substances and for filling data gaps in registrations submitted under the European Chemicals legislation, REACH¹. This approach has been applied successfully to small molecules for many years, but only recently has begun to be extended to cover the special requirements and the more complex and dynamic structures of Engineered Nanomaterials (ENMs). The overarching rationale behind the grouping/read across approach is that similar ENMs will have a similar toxicity behavior. Therefore, establishment of similarity measures and metrics is a prerequisite for any grouping/read-across variant, which is eventually applied for the prediction of properties of unknown ‘target’ ENMs using relevant information from known similar ‘source’ ENMs. Due to the complex structures of ENMs, definition of similarity is not trivial. Several perspectives of ENM characterisation can be taken into account that may define multiple levels of similarity (physicochemical, biological, kinetics etc.).

The NanoCommons project has put particular emphasis on the development and integration of grouping/read-across approaches having identified this lack as a significant barrier to progress in the field and to commercialisation of nanotechnologies. A number of methodologies have been developed based on the application of advanced nanoinformatics tools. Particular emphasis is given to the integration of the Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) concept, either by adapting methods for the prediction of Molecular Initiating Events (MIE) or by grouping ENMs based on their potential to trigger AOPs. Deliverable 6.2 presents these methodologies, which are summarised as follows:

- A series of methodologies and tools have been created, which implement and automate the comprehensive stepwise read-across strategy developed by the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) specifically for ENMs. In particular, mathematical programming algorithms have been developed for automating and optimizing the time-consuming step of establishing an efficient grouping hypothesis.
- Machine learning methodologies have been used to define similarity metrics among ENMs and to eventually define groups and neighborhoods of similar ENMs (nanofoms, and sets of nanofoms to use the ECHA terminology).
- Aggregated similarity scores have been defined in the context of the GUIDEnano tool based on ENM physicochemical properties such as chemical composition, impurities, crystalline form, aggregate size, particle size, shape and density.
- An AOP-based grouping strategy has been developed, by combining toxicogenomics data analysis, the application of the Benchmark Dose (BMD) on individual genes and information about genes and pathways relative to specific AOPs.

¹ Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals;
<https://echa.europa.eu/regulations/reach/legislation>

Introduction

Predictive modelling is an *in silico* approach that can be used for hazard assessment of engineered nanomaterials (ENMs), when there is an absence of experimental toxicology data. Predictive models can produce reliable estimations of toxicity-related endpoints much faster and with reduced cost compared to *in vivo* methods and, most importantly, do not involve animal testing. Over the past few years, the nanosafety community has encouraged the development of such alternative non-testing methods for the toxicological investigation of ENMs. These computer-aided methods aim to contribute to the prioritization of ENMs for safety evaluation and to support regulatory decision-making. One successful approach (Winkler *et al.*, 2013) is the adaptation of the quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) modeling methodologies to the special requirements of ENMs, which arise due to their complex and dynamic structures. The produced models are presented in the literature as nanoQSARs or QNARs (quantitative nanostructure-activity relationship) models. NanoCommons has developed comprehensive infrastructure for supporting all the steps required to generate nanoQSAR models (creation of training and test datasets, data preprocessing, model training and validation, tools for exposing models as web services, tools for preparing the necessary model reporting and prediction forms, i.e., the QMRF and QPRF) and already hosts many nanoQSAR models in the Jaqpot and Enalos platforms as presented in detail in Deliverable 5.4.

Grouping/read-across is an alternative approach for predictive modelling, which can be used when not enough samples are available for QSAR modelling (more than 20 distinct ENM samples are needed to train a QSAR model). The read-across concept is based on the empirical knowledge that similar materials may exhibit comparable properties thus, the estimation of the hazardous effects of non-tested ENMs can be achieved using data within a group of comparable ENMs (Gajewicz *et al.*, 2017a, Oomen *et al.*, 2015, Lamon *et al.*, 2018). Grouping/read-across approaches have been applied to small molecules during the last 20 years, but recently this type of approach is showing inevitable growth in filling toxicological gaps for ENMs (Cronin *et al.*, 2019). ECHA has developed the Read-Across Assessment Framework (RAAF), which presents a detailed workflow for performing grouping/read-across (see Figure 1). This workflow has been adapted to the special needs and requirements arising from the more complex and multi-perspective characterisation of ENMs compared to small molecules (ECHA, 2015, ECHA, 2017, Schultz *et al.*, 2015, Landvik *et al.*, 2018, Kuempel *et al.*, 2012).

The NanoCommons infrastructure has integrated a number of tools that can be used for searching for similar ENMs and for estimating toxicity of ENMs based on grouping/read-across approaches. This deliverable presents all these methodologies in detail. Many of these approaches take into consideration the emerging concept of AOPs, either by grouping ENMs based on the activation of specific AOPs or by taking into account corona formation around ENMs to predict AOP related events, like cell uptake. Many of the tools presented in this report are accompanied by Graphical User Interfaces (GUIs) which allow end-users to have direct and easy access to these approaches, via the NanoCommons service provision and/or Transnational Access platforms.

Existing grouping/read-across approaches for filling toxicological data gaps

Central to the grouping/read across philosophy is the workflow proposed by ECHA (Figure 1), which consists of seven well defined steps (ECHA, 2017):

1. Determination of the structural characteristics of ENMs (composition, including surface chemistry and any impurities, size, shape etc.).
2. Development of an initial grouping hypothesis that correlates an endpoint (e.g. a toxicity index) to different behavior and reactivity properties. Assignment of the samples into groups.
3. Gathering of the above properties (depending on the grouping hypothesis) for each ENM.
4. Construction of a data matrix including properties and endpoints.
5. Assessment of the applicability of the approach using computational techniques and data gap filling. If no regular pattern emerges, an alternative grouping hypothesis must be proposed (step 2).
6. Where the grouping hypothesis is robust, but adequate data are not available, additional testing should be considered to complete the datasets.
7. Justification of the method and completion of the method documentation.

Figure 1. Step-wise grouping/read-across approach proposed by ECHA in Appendix R.6-1 for nanoforms, from the Guidance on QSARs and Grouping of Chemicals (ECHA, 2019).

The development of a read-across scheme typically assumes a hypothesis, which is evaluated and assessed in terms of its adequacy to fill data gaps. The read-across hypothesis involves both the selection of the most informative descriptors that can predict the endpoint of interest and the definition of the source ENMs that can be considered as neighbors to the target ENM. This procedure is iterated in a trial-and-error fashion until a hypothesis producing successful read-across predictions is determined. The procedure is time-consuming and, due to the complexity of the problem, it does

not guarantee that the produced read-across model is optimal.

There are two conceptual approaches underpinning the read-across framework, supported by ECHA and the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD); the analogue and the category/grouping approach. In the category approach, it is assumed that structural similarity between ENMs may lead to the expression of similar (eco)toxicological and biological activity. Thus, ENMs that have a regular pattern in their structural characteristics can be considered as one group and read-across predictions may refer to the whole group whereas, an analogue approach can be applied within the group for sample-specific toxicity estimation. In the analogue approach, regular patterns are not obvious in the structural characteristics of a set of ENMs. In this case the search for similar ENMs through read-across prediction methodologies is restricted to a limited area of the data space and it is based either on experts' critical judgment, or on computational methods that mathematically measure ENMs similarity. In that particular case, a "local" interpolation methodology can be applied to the data for toxicity/property estimation. However, the boundaries between the two approaches are still unclear and depend on the number of available samples (Varsou *et al.*, 2017, Varsou *et al.*, 2019a, Helma *et al.*, 2017, Giusti *et al.*, 2019, Gajewicz *et al.*, 2017b, Gajewicz *et al.*, 2015).

Several read-across tools and methods for the preliminary hazard assessment of ENMs have been proposed in the literature (Oomen *et al.*, 2015). Gajewicz *et al.* (2017a) proposed a novel quantitative read-across (QRA) approach for data gap-filling of ENMs using the one-point-slope, the two-point formula and the equation of a plane passing through three points. Their Nano-QRA model proved to have high predictive capabilities, when tested with the same dataset used by Puzyn *et al.* (2011). Helma *et al.* (2019) recently introduced the nano-lazar framework for ENM read-across predictions. The similarity levels for the selection of neighbours is based on the Tanimoto/Jaccard index and on weighted cosine similarity. Three local regression algorithms are available; weighted local average, weighted partial least squares regression and weighted random forests. Helma *et al.* (2019) tested the performance of their methods using the dataset initially presented by Walkey *et al.* (2014) consisting of 121 gold and silver ENMs that are characterized by physicochemical descriptors, their protein corona fingerprints (PCF) and by MP2D fingerprints calculated for core and coating compounds with defined chemical structures using the MOLPRINT 2D similarity searching software². They reported R² values equal to 0.68 for the prediction of cell association with human A549 cells, using only the protein corona fingerprints and the weighted random forest algorithm, in a 10-fold cross validation scheme. Varsou *et al.* (2017) presented the **toxFlow** web application, which integrates physicochemical, omics and biology data for read-across toxicity prediction of ENMs. Neighbour selection is based either on the cosine similarity between ENMs or a distance metric (Euclidean, Manhattan). Using only the gold ENMs of the Walkey *et al.* (2014) study and performing enrichment analysis of the PCF data prior to read-across, Varsou *et al.* reported R² values of 0.97 in the toxicity prediction, by employing a weighted average algorithm and a leave-one-out validation scheme. Very recently, Lamon *et al.* (2018) and Aschberger *et al.* (2019) presented case studies applying the ECHA RAAF framework for the read-across prediction of hazard endpoints of nanoforms of TiO₂ and of Multi-Walled Carbon NanoTubes (MWCNTs), respectively. The first of these studies has been released as an official OECD document (OECD, 2018).

² <https://bmi.cchmc.org/resources/software/molprint-2d>

European Union (EU) funded projects, such as ITS-NANO and NanoMILE have considered the modification of physicochemical properties (e.g. hydrophilicity, zeta potential, agglomeration) during the life cycle of the ENMs (Stone *et al.*, 2014; Lynch *et al.*, 2014; Briffa *et al.*, 2018; Mitrano *et al.*, 2015) which may change the ENM behavior, fate and hazard. The project MARINA introduced a kinetic approach (e.g. uptake, distribution, biopersistence), considering the evolution of ENM physicochemical properties in different medium and for different exposure routes that could influence their hazard along their life cycle. Following the same approach, the nanoGRAVUR (BMBF, 2015–2018) project developed a framework for grouping of ENMs as a function of the exposure population (occupational, consumer and environmental). The framework is based on Tier 1, intrinsic physicochemical properties (what they are), Tier 2 extrinsic physico-chemical properties, release from nano-enabled products, *in vitro* assays with cells (where they go; what they do) and Tier 3 case-specific tests, potentially *in vivo* studies to substantiate the similarity within groups or application-specific exposure testing.

Currently the [GRACIOUS](#) project is improving the above mentioned approaches to generate a highly innovative science-based framework to enable practical application of grouping and read-across to inform regulatory risk assessment and hazard classification of ENMs and nanofibres (NFs). The framework will be delivered both as a guidance document and an E-tool to support various key stakeholders (regulatory and industrial) in the identification of grouping hypothesis and their validation through the application of Integrated Approach to Testing and Assessment (IATA). IATAs rely on an integrated analysis of existing and new information using testing strategies that aim to reduce and replace (when possible) the need for animal testing by promoting the use of modelling, *in vitro* and cell-free tests. IATAs will cover all the domains of relevance for risk assessment: the environmental release across the ENM and product lifecycle, and human exposure, physicochemical identity, environmental fate, uptake and toxicokinetics and human and environmental toxicity.

Biological Similarity - Adverse Outcome Pathways

Many grouping/read-across approaches rely on physicochemical similarity only. There are cases however, where small changes in the molecular structure can lead to a radical shift in toxic behaviour. To address this, the consideration of biological similarity can provide an additional level for defining the overall similarity among ENMs, thus increasing the accuracy and robustness of read-across predictions. The definition of biological similarity can be based on both omics and protein corona formulations, which are unique to ENMs. It can be extended to take into account the concept of AOPs, which are briefly defined in the rest of this subsection.

The concept of ‘mechanism of action’ (MOA) can be illuminating, since it describes in detail the chain of events that link a chemical input with the *in vivo* response, with in-depth knowledge of the causal and temporal relationships involved (Borgert *et al.*, 2004). However, defining a MOA is a challenging task, mainly because of the lack of the experimental data needed to describe the temporal changes in detail, which in turn means that using an MOA to define a group of substances with similar toxicological effects may not be feasible.

A more flexible alternative to the MOA is that of the AOP. According to the first definition of an AOP, in the context of ecotoxicological risk assessment, it is “a conceptual construct that portrays existing knowledge concerning the linkage between a direct MIE and an Adverse Outcome (AO)”. This representation captures the causal link(s) between the MIE and the AO via a series of key events (KE), that happen at different, multiple levels of biological organization targeted by a risk assessment process (Ankley *et al.* 2010) as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. An example portraying the typical AOP scheme, starting from the Molecular Initiating Event (MIE) which induces a series of Key Events (KEs), that are connected by Key Event Relationships (KERs) and result in a single Adverse Outcome (AO) (Gerloff *et al.*, 2017).

The MIE is a measurable event that describes the interaction of the toxicant with a biological system at the molecular level, which stems from the chemical properties of the toxicant and initiates the sequence of events that lead to the manifestation of the AO. If the structure of a compound can cause a MIE, then it can be causally linked to the AO following the flow of causal relationships that are reflected in the AOP structure.

An important initiative taken by the OECD is the establishment of the AOP knowledge base (AOP-KB), with the goal of dissemination and development of AOPs. The platform intends to share existing and develop new AOPs, and collects data for creating quantitative relationships between the AOP building blocks. The AOP-KB consists of four independently developed platforms: AOP-Wiki, AOP Xplorer, Effectopedia and Intermediate Effects DB (Wittwehr *et al.*, 2015).

The toxFlow Grouping/Read-Across Tool

The ECHA workflow presented in a previous section is a concrete methodology that has already been used in specific case studies in the nanotoxicity area. However, it is not supported by a tool that can assist users to perform all of the steps from a single application. Furthermore, it involves a time-consuming trial and error method, especially regarding the formation of the grouping hypothesis, where the user needs to go through the workflow and if the results are not satisfactory, he/she needs to define a different hypothesis. A number of tools that overcome these limitations have been developed by NTUA and are now integrated into the NanoCommons infrastructure. NTUA has based the development of these tools on transforming the basic concept of the ECHA methodology into a modelling problem that can be described in mathematical terms and can be solved using advanced computational techniques, such as artificial intelligence algorithms and mathematical programming methods. The basic concept of this formulation is depicted in Figure 3, which clearly presents the four basic ingredients of defining the read-across problem:

1. Selection of the most relevant independent variables, represented by a binary vector, whose length is the number of variables included in the ENM fingerprint. A one (1) value means that the specific variable is important and should be involved in defining the neighbours, while a zero (0) value means that the variable does not affect considerably the specific end-point and is excluded from the set of important variables.
2. The metric that defines the distance between two ENMs in the ENM-hyper space. The Euclidean distance is shown in Figure 3, but many alternative options can be considered (see Deliverable 4.6 - *Description of tools for automated data mining* for further details).
3. The threshold that defines the neighborhood around an ENM, i.e. all the ENMs whose distance from the query ENM is equal to, or lower than, the threshold are considered as similar and are used in the calculation of the read-across prediction.
4. The mathematical formula that computes the read-across prediction. For a continuous end-point, the weighted average shown in Figure 3 is the typical choice.

Figure 3. A schematic view of the read-across problem using one similarity measure. The threshold is the radius around the location of the reference ENM in the ensure nanomaterial space defines its neighborhood and the similar ENMs.

Figure 4. A schematic view of the read-across problem using two similarity measures. Two thresholds in the radii around the location of the ENM in the nanomaterial space are defined. The more conservartive (smaller radius) defines its neighborhood and the similar ENMs which can be used for read-across.

The set-up of the mathematical definition of the read-across problem was further extended by separating the descriptors of the ENMs into different categories (e.g. physicochemical, biological, biokinetics etc.). Using this approach, different vectors are constructed for each group and different distances and thresholds define the various similarities and neighborhoods around the ENMs as shown in Figure 4. The advantage of this extension is that it considers explicitly the multi-perspective characterization of ENMs, by defining multiple thresholds relative to different similarity criteria and ensuring that two ENMs are considered as neighbours only if they satisfy all similarity requirements.

The first tool in this series of read-across methodologies, developed by NTUA, is the **toxFlow** tool that was originally developed in the eNanoMapper project and is now integrated into the NanoCommons modelling infrastructure. The **toxFlow** tool is a web based R-Shiny implementation of the abovementioned grouping/read-across approach, where the user can manually select most of the parameters involved in the construction of the read-across problem. More specifically, the toxicity endpoint prediction of the target ENM can be performed using the weighted average of the corresponding values of the neighbour ENMs, i.e. neighbouring substances of every target ENM are selected by calculating pairwise similarity measures with all available ENMs and by excluding those ENMs for which the similarity measure does not fulfill a predefined threshold. The proposed workflow assumes that a complete training data set is available, i.e., a set of ENMs for which the toxicity endpoint values are known, as described in Varsou *et al.* (2017).

If two types of descriptors are available (e.g. physicochemical and biological), similarity measures are calculated between all ENMs separately for the available physicochemical and biological data. For each ENM in the available set, the ENMs for which both similarity measures satisfy predefined corresponding thresholds are selected as neighbours. Therefore, in order to characterize two ENMs as similar they need to satisfy both physicochemical and biological similarity criteria. Three options for defining the similarity measure can be considered: the cosine similarity (Eq. 1), the Manhattan distance (Eq. 2), and the Euclidean distance (Eq. 3)

$$CS_{A,B} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N A_i B_i}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N A_i^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N B_i^2}} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

$$MD_{A,B} = \sum_{i=1}^N |A_i - B_i| \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

$$ED_{A,B} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (A_i - B_i)^2} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

where, A and B are vectors containing the physicochemical or biological descriptors of the two ENMs on which the similarity measure is computed; A_i , is the i^{th} element of vector A ; B_i , is the i^{th} element of

vector B; and N is the size of A and B vectors.

The two distance metrics are transformed to similarity measures according to Eq. 4 shown below, ensuring that all similarity values range between 0 and 1.

$$\text{sim}_{A,B} = \begin{cases} \text{CS}_{A,B} & \text{for cosine similarity} \\ \frac{1}{1 + \text{MD}_{A,B}} & \text{for Manhattan distance} \\ \frac{1}{1 + \text{ED}_{A,B}} & \text{for Euclidean distance} \end{cases} \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

The predicted read-across value (RAV) for a reference ENM in the training set is calculated using only its selected neighbours as shown in Eq. 5, where the weighting factors are based on either physicochemical or biological similarity measures (Varsou *et al.*, 2017).

$$\text{RAV} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{L_{\text{ref}}} (\text{sim}_{i,\text{ref}} \times \text{tox}_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^{L_{\text{ref}}} \text{sim}_{i,\text{ref}}} \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

where, *ref* is the reference ENM; L_{ref} is the total number of neighbors for the reference ENM; i is the i^{th} neighbor of the reference ENM; tox_i is the known toxicity endpoint value of the i^{th} neighbor; and $\text{sim}_{i,\text{ref}}$ is the weighting factor (similarity) corresponding to the i^{th} neighbor of the reference ENM, as defined in Eq. 4.

toxFlow is equipped with functionalities for performing enrichment analysis of omics data, when such data are part of the available dataset. The objective is to produce a reduced dataset, which can be more easily handled when performing the read-across prediction. Through a sequential analysis workflow, users can filter omics data using enrichment scores and incorporate their findings into a correlation-based read-across technique for predicting the toxicity of a substance based on its analogs. Either embedded or in-house gene signature libraries can be used for enrichment analysis. The suggested approach can be used for toxicity prediction of diverse chemical entities; as well as multi-end-point characterized ENMs and selects their neighbours based on both physicochemical and biological similarity criteria. In addition, visualization options are offered to interactively explore correlation patterns in the data, whereby results can be exported for further analysis. **toxFlow** is accessible at <http://147.102.86.129:3838/toxflow>.

The application consists of three main parts, in three different tabs (as can be seen in Figure 5). The first two parts can be used independently, while the third part depends on model training thus, it cannot be executed prior to the second part:

- Gene Set Variation Analysis (GSVA): In this part, the user can employ the provided tools in order to perform GSVA (Hänzelmann *et al.*, 2013) through the samples of an expression data set. Different omics data types could be analyzed (genomics, proteomics). Using GSVA analysis tools

D6.2 AOP-based grouping of ENMs

a group of all statistically significant gene sets is presented in a table along with corresponding acyclic graphs and heatmaps, also providing links to pathway databases whenever possible.

- Read-across training: In this part training of a toxicity-prediction model is performed, via read across techniques and the leave-one-out cross-validation method. Using read-across techniques a table that contains all ENMs with a successful prediction for the toxicity index is presented, as well as correlation coefficient R^2 (as an index of successful prediction) and a diagram of ENMs with their neighbours (the ENMs' universe).
- Read-across prediction: After model training, users can predict the unknown value of toxicity indices of an ENMs' data set. After prediction, a table that contains the predicted value of the toxicity index for all the ENMs is presented along with the ENMs universe diagram.

The application is well-documented therefore interested users can easily access and use it independently (i.e. via the service mode of Transnational Access under NanoCommons). In the next paragraphs the **toxFlow** application is demonstrated using the dataset from Walkey *et al.* (2014) which consists of PCF as well as physicochemical descriptors for 84 gold ENMs with diameters 15, 30 and 60 nm, from LC/MS-MS analysis experiments. These ENMs were incubated with A549 cells (human lung epithelial cancer cells). This case study allows to illustrate the full capabilities of the **toxFlow** application, as the total set of descriptors is separated into two groups (physicochemical and biological), and the GSVA methodology can be applied to preprocess and reduce the PCFs. Furthermore, cell uptake (cell association) which is the end point in the dataset is very relevant to the concept of AOPs, because it is actually an MIE. The landing page of **toxFlow** is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. User interface of the toxFlow application. On the top ribbon are shown the three tabs - one for every main part of the workflow.

toxFlow: Gene Set Variation Analysis (GSVA)

Before running the GSVA analysis, the user should import two files in a specific format: The first file (**Biological data**) must contain the samples of an expression data set. The second file (**Data classification**) must contain the classification of the samples into categories, which will be used for the creation of the design matrix. A demo dataset for anionic-cationic classification is also available, so that the users can see an example of the analysis. The supplied data set can be normalized, by clicking on the appropriate checkbox.

Furthermore, the user can select from a drop-down list the **Accession ID** of the gene or protein names (Uniprot, EntrezID, RefSeq or Symbol). The user can select between the C5: GO gene sets, MF: GO molecular function (GO-MF) and CTD Disease-GO molecular function associations (CTD-MF) gene set collections. GO-MF is taken from MSigDB v5.1 and contains 396 gene sets in GO (Gene Ontology) terms and CTD-MF is taken from Comparative Toxicogenomics Database and contains 3,992 gene sets in GO IDs. The user can also import another gene set collection in order to perform the analysis.

Additionally, in the **Number of bootstraps** field the user can choose the number of bootstrap iterations to be performed in the GSVA function, and in **Gene set size** can control the minimum and maximum size of the resulting gene sets. In **Adjusted p-value cut off** the user can control the threshold of the adjusted p-value in order to select the significant gene sets that result from the linear analysis of the GSVA enrichment scores. Finally, in **GO mapping for acyclic graph** the user can choose between GOMFPARENTS and GOMFCHILDREN, as the main parameter of the acyclic graph that depicts the significant gene sets and the hierarchical relations with other gene sets from the Gene Ontology.

Once all the required files are uploaded, by clicking **Run** analysis the application performs the analysis, according to the parameters above. After running the analysis, the application exports a table that contains the significant gene sets, their GO IDs, their size, the adjusted p-value based on the Benjamini-Hochberg multiple correction method of the linear model, and the counts (the number of genes in the initial data set that are found in the gene sets of the gene set collection). In addition the application produces a heatmap with the gene sets that result from the GSVA and an acyclic graph (see example in Figure 6). All results can be downloaded for further analysis.

toxFlow
GSVA
Read-across training
Read-across prediction
Help

Gene set variation analysis

Ready to run analysis

Input data Parameters of analysis

Gene set collection:
Chemical-GO enriched associations (from Comparative Toxicogenomics Database)

Number of bootstraps:
1

Gene set size:
1 6000

Adjusted p-value cut off:
0.001 0.05

GO mapping for acyclic graph:
GOMFPARENTS

Run analysis

Differentially expressed gene sets

Show 10 entries Search:

	GOMFID	Term	p-value	Size	Counts
1	GO:0005244	voltage gated ion channel activity	6.50151809365574e-13	75	2
2	GO:0005216	ion channel activity	9.0908561732656e-13	115	1
3	GO:0005272	sodium channel activity	9.0908561732656e-13	23	1
4	GO:0031402	sodium ion binding	9.0908561732656e-13	11	1
5	GO:0005248	voltage gated sodium channel activity	9.0908561732656e-13	17	1
6	GO:0046983	protein dimerization activity	1.89835992115254e-12	124	3
7	GO:0051879	hsp90 protein binding	6.12416208617797e-11	25	2
8	GO:0032403	protein complex binding	1.71188918105376e-10	249	5
9	GO:0008502	melatonin receptor activity	2.00008758003609e-10	4	1
10	GO:0019003	gdp binding	2.06637048654093e-9	27	1

Showing 1 to 10 of 134 entries Previous 1 2 3 4 5 ... 14 Next

Download

Gene sets-genes heatmap

Download

GO directed acyclic graph

Download

Figure 6. An example of GSVA results and outputs - the list of differentially expressed genes, the gene set heatmap and the GO-directed acyclic graph.

toxFlow: Read-across training

The user must upload two .csv files in the application: The first one (**Physicochemical data**) must contain the values of physicochemical descriptors and the second one (**Biological data**) must contain the samples of an expression data set. Both files must contain the values of the toxicity index, which will be predicted by the model. A demo dataset from Walkey *et al.* (2014) is provided as an example. For similarity definition the physicochemical descriptors and protein corona composition data were used, while cell association was used as the endpoint. The user can select if the physicochemical and expression data should be normalized.

Also, the user can select whether only the significant genes or proteins (according to the data) from the GSVA analysis will be used. It is implied that in the previous section the user will have analyzed the same biological data.

In order to reduce the noise of the data for the analysis, the user can filter the attributes according to the absolute value of their correlation to the endpoint. For this purpose, two sliders are available in order to define the filtering level of the absolute values of the attribute's correlation to the endpoint. For the estimation of similarity between ENMs, the user can choose from a drop-down list one of the following options: cosine similarity, Manhattan and Euclidean distance.

The user can define the physicochemical and biological threshold that controls the selection of neighboring ENMs from numeric inputs. Finally, in **Prediction base** the user can choose if the prediction will be calculated on a physicochemical or biological basis. By pressing the training button, the model training begins. The user can also visualize the ENMs "universe": the user can choose a reference ENM and observe its neighbours in color code, by adjusting the physicochemical and biological thresholds. Also, by selecting **Nanoparticles' diameter** and **Nanoparticles' classification** the user can upload two corresponding files and observe the reference's neighbours according to their size and their classification.

The analysis produces a table that contains all ENMs with a successful prediction for the toxicity index, with the actual and the predicted value of this index. The prediction value is calculated using the same units as the actual values. The user can download this table in the form of a .csv file. In addition, the correlation coefficient R^2 is presented, as well as the ENMs' universe diagram.

Figure 7 shows an example of a read-across trained model, using the Walkey *et al.* dataset previously filtered by GSVA (the GSVA specifications are presented in Figure 6). Similarities were calculated using Euclidean distance and the two thresholds were manually tuned to 0.5 for physicochemical and 0.54 for biological descriptors. Predictions were calculated using physicochemical similarity measures as weighting factors. The correlation coefficient R^2 value during leave-one-out cross-validation was equal to 0.973. Predictions for all samples with a successful prediction are presented in the produced table. The neighbours' universe for ENM G15.AUT is also presented. We can observe that only one neighbour of the same diameter and classification was used for the read-across prediction. In general, users can tune the threshold values of the diagram and observe the neighbours for each ENM according to these values and the selected similarity metric. Therefore, according to these observations they can later tune the input threshold values and acquire more targeted predictions.

toxFlow: Read-across prediction

The last part of the application can be used after the read across training. In that way, the toxicity index of a data set can be predicted, when all the physicochemical and biological indices that were used in model training are known values. The user must upload two .csv files in the application: The first one (**Physicochemical data**) must contain the values of physicochemical descriptors. The second one (**Biological data**) must contain the samples of an expression data set.

Clicking on the **Prediction** button begins the prediction process. The user can visualize the ENMs “universe” as described before.

The analysis produces a table that contains the predicted value of the toxicity index for all the ENMs, which the user can download in the form of a .csv file. In addition, the ENMs universe diagram is presented (Figure 8).

The screenshot displays the 'toxFlow' application interface for 'Read-across prediction'. The top navigation bar includes 'toxFlow', 'GSVA', 'Read-across training', 'Read-across prediction', and 'Help'. The left sidebar contains a 'Toxicity endpoint prediction' section with a download icon and 'Ready for visualization' status. It includes fields for 'Physicochemical data' (phChem_prediction.csv) and 'Biological data' (bio_prediction.csv), both with 'Upload complete' indicators. A 'Prediction' button is present. Below is the 'Nanoparticle's universe' section with a 'Reference nanoparticle' field set to '1' and checkboxes for 'Nanoparticles' diameter' and 'Nanoparticles' classification'. There are also input fields for 'Physicochemical thresholds' (0.5) and 'Biological thresholds' (0.54), along with a 'Visualization' button.

The central 'Prediction Table' shows two entries:

#	Nanoparticle's ID	Read across value
1	P1	-5.62878912395847
2	P2	-5.08379702504618

Below the table, it indicates 'Showing 1 to 2 of 2 entries' and provides 'Previous', '1', and 'Next' navigation options, along with a 'Download' button.

The right sidebar features a search bar and a 'Nanoparticles' universe' diagram. The diagram is a circular network graph with numerous nodes labeled with alphanumeric codes (e.g., G1S, G1E, G1F, G1G, G1H, G1I, G1J, G1K, G1L, G1M, G1N, G1O, G1P, G1Q, G1R, G1S, G1T, G1U, G1V, G1W, G1X, G1Y, G1Z, G1AA, G1AB, G1AC, G1AD, G1AE, G1AF, G1AG, G1AH, G1AI, G1AJ, G1AK, G1AL, G1AM, G1AN, G1AO, G1AP, G1AQ, G1AR, G1AS, G1AT, G1AU, G1AV, G1AW, G1AX, G1AY, G1AZ, G1BA, G1BB, G1BC, G1BD, G1BE, G1BF, G1BG, G1BH, G1BI, G1BJ, G1BK, G1BL, G1BM, G1BN, G1BO, G1BP, G1BQ, G1BR, G1BS, G1BT, G1BU, G1BV, G1BW, G1BX, G1BY, G1BZ, G1CA, G1CB, G1CC, G1CD, G1CE, G1CF, G1CG, G1CH, G1CI, G1CJ, G1CK, G1CL, G1CM, G1CN, G1CO, G1CP, G1CQ, G1CR, G1CS, G1CT, G1CU, G1CV, G1CW, G1CX, G1CY, G1CZ, G1DA, G1DB, G1DC, G1DD, G1DE, G1DF, G1DG, G1DH, G1DI, G1DJ, G1DK, G1DL, G1DM, G1DN, G1DO, G1DP, G1DQ, G1DR, G1DS, G1DT, G1DU, G1DV, G1DW, G1DX, G1DY, G1DZ, G1EA, G1EB, G1EC, G1ED, G1EE, G1EF, G1EG, G1EH, G1EI, G1EJ, G1EK, G1EL, G1EM, G1EN, G1EO, G1EP, G1EQ, G1ER, G1ES, G1ET, G1EU, G1EV, G1EW, G1EX, G1EY, G1EZ, G1FA, G1FB, G1FC, G1FD, G1FE, G1FF, G1FG, G1FH, G1FI, G1FJ, G1FK, G1FL, G1FM, G1FN, G1FO, G1FP, G1FQ, G1FR, G1FS, G1FT, G1FU, G1FV, G1FW, G1FX, G1FY, G1FZ, G1GA, G1GB, G1GC, G1GD, G1GE, G1GF, G1GG, G1GH, G1GI, G1GJ, G1GK, G1GL, G1GM, G1GN, G1GO, G1GP, G1GQ, G1GR, G1GS, G1GT, G1GU, G1GV, G1GW, G1GX, G1GY, G1GZ, G1HA, G1HB, G1HC, G1HD, G1HE, G1HF, G1HG, G1HH, G1HI, G1HJ, G1HK, G1HL, G1HM, G1HN, G1HO, G1HP, G1HQ, G1HR, G1HS, G1HT, G1HU, G1HV, G1HW, G1HX, G1HY, G1HZ, G1IA, G1IB, G1IC, G1ID, G1IE, G1IF, G1IG, G1IH, G1II, G1IJ, G1IK, G1IL, G1IM, G1IN, G1IO, G1IP, G1IQ, G1IR, G1IS, G1IT, G1IU, G1IV, G1IW, G1IX, G1IY, G1IZ, G1JA, G1JB, G1JC, G1JD, G1JE, G1JF, G1JG, G1JH, G1JI, G1JJ, G1JK, G1JL, G1JM, G1JN, G1JO, G1JP, G1JQ, G1JR, G1JS, G1JT, G1JU, G1JV, G1JW, G1JX, G1JY, G1JZ, G1KA, G1KB, G1KC, G1KD, G1KE, G1KF, G1KG, G1KH, G1KI, G1KJ, G1KK, G1KL, G1KM, G1KN, G1KO, G1KP, G1KQ, G1KR, G1KS, G1KT, G1KU, G1KV, G1KW, G1KX, G1KY, G1KZ, G1LA, G1LB, G1LC, G1LD, G1LE, G1LF, G1LG, G1LH, G1LI, G1LJ, G1LK, G1LL, G1LM, G1LN, G1LO, G1LP, G1LQ, G1LR, G1LS, G1LT, G1LU, G1LV, G1LW, G1LX, G1LY, G1LZ, G1MA, G1MB, G1MC, G1MD, G1ME, G1MF, G1MG, G1MH, G1MI, G1MJ, G1MK, G1ML, G1MN, G1MO, G1MP, G1MQ, G1MR, G1MS, G1MT, G1MU, G1MV, G1MW, G1MX, G1MY, G1MZ, G1NA, G1NB, G1NC, G1ND, G1NE, G1NF, G1NG, G1NH, G1NI, G1NJ, G1NK, G1NL, G1NM, G1NN, G1NO, G1NP, G1NQ, G1NR, G1NS, G1NT, G1NU, G1NV, G1NW, G1NX, G1NY, G1NZ, G1OA, G1OB, G1OC, G1OD, G1OE, G1OF, G1OG, G1OH, G1OI, G1OJ, G1OK, G1OL, G1OM, G1ON, G1OO, G1OP, G1OQ, G1OR, G1OS, G1OT, G1OU, G1OV, G1OW, G1OX, G1OY, G1OZ, G1PA, G1PB, G1PC, G1PD, G1PE, G1PF, G1PG, G1PH, G1PI, G1PJ, G1PK, G1PL, G1PM, G1PN, G1PO, G1PP, G1PQ, G1PR, G1PS, G1PT, G1PU, G1PV, G1PW, G1PX, G1PY, G1PZ, G1QA, G1QB, G1QC, G1QD, G1QE, G1QF, G1QG, G1QH, G1QI, G1QJ, G1QK, G1QL, G1QM, G1QN, G1QO, G1QP, G1QQ, G1QR, G1QS, G1QT, G1QU, G1QV, G1QW, G1QX, G1QY, G1QZ, G1RA, G1RB, G1RC, G1RD, G1RE, G1RF, G1RG, G1RH, G1RI, G1RJ, G1RK, G1RL, G1RM, G1RN, G1RO, G1RP, G1RQ, G1RR, G1RS, G1RT, G1RU, G1RV, G1RW, G1RX, G1RY, G1RZ, G1SA, G1SB, G1SC, G1SD, G1SE, G1SF, G1SG, G1SH, G1SI, G1SJ, G1SK, G1SL, G1SM, G1SN, G1SO, G1SP, G1SQ, G1SR, G1SS, G1ST, G1SU, G1SV, G1SW, G1SX, G1SY, G1SZ, G1TA, G1TB, G1TC, G1TD, G1TE, G1TF, G1TG, G1TH, G1TI, G1TJ, G1TK, G1TL, G1TM, G1TN, G1TO, G1TP, G1TQ, G1TR, G1TS, G1TT, G1TU, G1TV, G1TW, G1TX, G1TY, G1TZ, G1UA, G1UB, G1UC, G1UD, G1UE, G1UF, G1UG, G1UH, G1UI, G1UJ, G1UK, G1UL, G1UM, G1UN, G1UO, G1UP, G1UQ, G1UR, G1US, G1UT, G1UU, G1UV, G1UW, G1UX, G1UY, G1UZ, G1VA, G1VB, G1VC, G1VD, G1VE, G1VF, G1VG, G1VH, G1VI, G1VJ, G1VK, G1VL, G1VM, G1VN, G1VO, G1VP, G1VQ, G1VR, G1VS, G1VT, G1VU, G1VV, G1VW, G1VX, G1VY, G1VZ, G1WA, G1WB, G1WC, G1WD, G1WE, G1WF, G1WG, G1WH, G1WI, G1WJ, G1WK, G1WL, G1WM, G1WN, G1WO, G1WP, G1WQ, G1WR, G1WS, G1WT, G1WU, G1WV, G1WW, G1WX, G1WY, G1WZ, G1XA, G1XB, G1XC, G1XD, G1XE, G1XF, G1XG, G1XH, G1XI, G1XJ, G1XK, G1XL, G1XM, G1XN, G1XO, G1XP, G1XQ, G1XR, G1XS, G1XT, G1XU, G1XV, G1XW, G1XX, G1XY, G1XZ, G1YA, G1YB, G1YC, G1YD, G1YE, G1YF, G1YG, G1YH, G1YI, G1YJ, G1YK, G1YL, G1YM, G1YN, G1YO, G1YP, G1YQ, G1YR, G1YS, G1YT, G1YU, G1YV, G1YW, G1YX, G1YY, G1YZ, G1ZA, G1ZB, G1ZC, G1ZD, G1ZE, G1ZF, G1ZG, G1ZH, G1ZI, G1ZJ, G1ZK, G1ZL, G1ZM, G1ZN, G1ZO, G1ZP, G1ZQ, G1ZR, G1ZS, G1ZT, G1ZU, G1ZV, G1ZW, G1ZX, G1ZY, G1ZZ).

Figure 8. A screenshot of the toxFlow read-across predictions on unknown ENMs, visualised as the test ENMs universe diagram showing the ENMs that are used in the prediction (i.e., its neighbours).

Using the previously developed model, predictions have been made for an artificial dataset of ENMs. In this case the ENM’s universe diagram for each unknown sample depicts the neighbours of the unknown ENM in the training set.

The Apellis grouping/read-across application

As mentioned in the previous subsection, the **toxFlow** application is a user friendly web tool that allows a user to perform all steps required for calculating a read-across prediction. Its main limitation is that the user still needs to start with a grouping/read-across hypothesis regarding the variables that will be selected as important variables and the thresholds that define neighborhoods (sets) of similar ENMs.

As the next step in this series of grouping/read-across approaches, NTUA has developed a methodology which automates the process of searching over the solution space in order to find the read-across hypothesis that produces the best possible results in terms of prediction accuracy and number of ENMs for which predictions are obtained (Varsou *et al.*, 2019a). Thus, it overcomes a main drawback of existing approaches, which are based on manually trying different read-across hypotheses in an iterative, inefficient and time-consuming trial and error fashion. The main outcomes of the method are a reduced set of significant descriptors and a single or multiple threshold value(s) which rigorously define the boundaries around a query ENM, where neighboring ENMs are located. These two different goals are achieved simultaneously through the development of a Mixed Integer NonLinear Programming (MINLP) problem, where the objective is to minimize the Mean Squared Error (MSE) between the experimental values and the produced predictions with respect to selecting the most informative descriptors and defining the neighbour boundaries.

The formulation of the MINLP problem for a single similarity criterion has been shown in Deliverable 6.1. Here we present this formulation for two similarity criteria with a small alteration in the objective function (regularization term accompanied by a regularization factor $wfOF$, that controls the influence of the number of selected variables), but most importantly we present the strategy that was specifically developed for solving the problem, since the MINLP cannot be solved to optimality using standard mathematical programming algorithms.

MINLP formulation for read-across with two similarity criteria

Available data

The methodology assumes the availability of a dataset containing the values of L descriptors and the end-point for N ENMs. The descriptors are grouped into sets A and B containing L_A and L_B descriptors respectively. The data are first scaled using a standardization (e.g. Gaussian normalization) or a normalization (e.g. min-max) method, so that descriptors with substantially different numerical ranges contribute equally after the transformation to the overall analysis. The dataset is denoted by $\{\mathbf{xA}_i, \mathbf{xB}_i, y_i\}$, $i=1, \dots, N$, where $\{\mathbf{xA}_i\}$ is a vector containing the values of the L_A descriptors for the i^{th} ENM, $\{\mathbf{xB}_i\}$ is a vector containing the values of the L_B descriptors for the i^{th} ENM and y_i is the endpoint value of the i^{th} ENM.

Set of variables

The main outcomes of the MINLP problem are:

$attrA_l$: a binary variable indicating if the descriptor l is selected, $l=1, \dots, L_A$.

$attrB_l$: a binary variable indicating if the descriptor l is selected, $l=1, \dots, L_B$.

thr_A, thr_B : two continuous variables defining thresholds for the selection of neighbouring ENMs for the two similarity criteria. Only if both Euclidean distances between two ENMs are equal or less than the respective thresholds can these two ENMs be considered neighbours.

A number of additional variables are used for the construction of the MINLP problem:

$distA_{i,j}, distB_{i,j}$: two continuous variables containing the Euclidean distance between ENMs i and j , for the two similarity criteria $i=1, \dots, N, j=1, \dots, N$.

$neibA_{i,j}, neibB_{i,j}$: two binary variables taking the value of 1 if ENMs i and j are neighbours with respect to similarity criteria A or B and 0 if they are not, $i=1, \dots, N, j=1, \dots, N$.

$neib_{i,j}$: a binary variable taking the value of 1 if ENMs i and j are neighbours and 0 if they are not, $i=1, \dots, N, j=1, \dots, N$

$pred_i$: a binary variable taking the value of 1, if ENM i has at least one neighbour and 0 if it has no neighbours, $i=1, \dots, N$

\tilde{y}_i : a continuous variable containing the predicted endpoint read-across value for the i^{th} ENM, $i=1, \dots, N$.

Mathematical formulation

Set of constraints: Eqs. 6 and 7 compute the Euclidean distance between all pairs of ENMs taking into account only the selected descriptors:

$$distA_{i,j} = \sqrt{\sum_{\ell=1}^{L_A} attrA_{\ell} (xA_{i,\ell} - xA_{j,\ell})^2}, i = 1, \dots, N, j = 1, \dots, N, i \neq j \quad (\text{Eq. 6})$$

$$distB_{i,j} = \sqrt{\sum_{\ell=1}^{L_B} attrB_{\ell} (xB_{i,\ell} - xB_{j,\ell})^2}, i = 1, \dots, N, j = 1, \dots, N, i \neq j \quad (\text{Eq.7})$$

Eqs. 8-13 ensure that the two ENMs are considered as neighbours with respect to the different similarity criteria only if their Euclidean distance is lower than the threshold. In this case the binary variable takes the value of 1, otherwise the value 0 is assigned to this variable. In Eqs. 8 and 9, m is a small number (equal to 10^{-3}):

$$neibA_{i,j} \geq m(thr_A - distA_{i,j}), \forall i,j \in \{1, \dots, N\}, i \neq j \quad (\text{Eq.8})$$

$$1 - neibA_{i,j} \geq -m(thr_A - distA_{i,j}), \forall i,j \in \{1, \dots, N\}, i \neq j \quad (\text{Eq. 9})$$

$$neibA_{i,i} = 0, \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \quad (\text{Eq. 10})$$

$$neibB_{i,j} \geq m(thr_B - distB_{i,j}), \forall i,j \in \{1, \dots, N\}, i \neq j \quad (\text{Eq. 11})$$

$$1 - \text{neib}B_{i,j} \geq -m(\text{thr}_B - \text{dist}B_{i,j}), \forall i,j \in \{1, \dots, N\}, i \neq j \quad (\text{Eq. 12})$$

$$\text{neib}B_{i,i} = 0, \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \quad (\text{Eq. 13})$$

Eqs. 14-16 define two ENMs i and j as neighbors if they satisfy both similarity criteria, i.e. only if both $\text{neib}A_{i,j}$ and $\text{neib}B_{i,j}$ are equal to 1.

$$\text{neib}_{i,j} \geq \text{neib}A_{i,j} + \text{neib}B_{i,j} - 1, \forall i,j \in \{1, \dots, N\} \quad (\text{Eq. 14})$$

$$\text{neib}_{i,j} \leq \text{neib}A_{i,j}, \forall i,j \in \{1, \dots, N\} \quad (\text{Eq. 15})$$

$$\text{neib}_{i,j} \leq \text{neib}B_{i,j}, \forall i,j \in \{1, \dots, N\} \quad (\text{Eq. 16})$$

Eq. 17 computes the read-across predictions as weighted averages of the endpoint values of neighbour ENMs by selecting one distance metric (here we assume the metric based on group A):

$$\hat{y}_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^N y_j \frac{\text{neib}_{i,j}}{1 + \text{dist}A_{i,j}}}{\sum_{j=1}^N \frac{\text{neib}_{i,j}}{1 + \text{dist}A_{i,j}}}, \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \quad (\text{Eq. 17})$$

For ENMs without any neighbour, the prediction is obviously equal to 0 and it is not accepted. An additional constraint is used to guarantee that the percent of ENMs with at least one neighbour for which an endpoint prediction is produced is greater than or equal to a predefined percentage denoted by predFactor , as shown in Eqs. 18-20:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \text{pred}_i \geq \text{predFactor} N \quad (\text{Eq. 18})$$

$$\text{pred}_i \geq \text{neib}_{i,j}, \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\}, \forall j \in \{1, \dots, N\} \quad (\text{Eq. 19})$$

$$\text{pred}_i \leq \sum_{j=1}^N \text{neib}_{i,j}, \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \quad (\text{Eq. 20})$$

Objective function: The objective function to be minimized is the MSE between the endpoint read-across predictions and the actual endpoint values over all the ENMs with at least one neighbour plus a penalty on the number of selected attributes (Eqs. 21-22).

$$MSE = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^N pred_i} \sum_{i=1}^n pred_i (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (\text{Eq. 21})$$

$$OF = MSE + wf_{OF} \cdot \sum_{\ell=1}^L attr_{\ell} \quad (\text{Eq. 22})$$

Genetic Algorithm for the solution of the MINLP problem

Here we present the stochastic genetic algorithm (GA) that was developed for solving the MINLP problem. The development of GAs is "bio-inspired" from the principles of species evolution, and is based on the concept that living organisms are examples of successful optimization. The operational parameters of the GAs are summarised next and are directly linked to the biological processes of selection, crossover and mutation of genes:

- Potential solution (chromosome): The chromosome contains a sequence of genes with a length equal to the total number of variables.
- Group of potential solutions (population): A group of chromosomes (an even number).
- Iterations (generations): A number of cycles of selection, crossover and mutation between the potential solutions, leading to an optimal solution.
- Fitness evaluation (selection): A process of selection of chromosomes based on their calculated fitness. The reproduction of the fittest chromosomes in the next generation must be assured.
- Combination of two potential solutions (crossover): Reproduction operator is employed to exchange genes between two chromosomes, in a random point of crossover.
- Alteration of a potential solution (mutation): A process of alteration of the crossed chromosomes. According to a predefined probability value, the procedure inverts the value of each gene: 0 becomes 1 and vice versa (uniform mutation).
- Ensuring desirable evolution (elitism): During the creation of a new population with different biological processes, there is a chance of losing the chromosome with the highest score. This method forces the best chromosome to be included in the new population.
- Optimal solution (genome): A chromosome containing the combination of genes among the generations that leads to the optimal solution.

The particular GA developed in this work uses the parameters depicted in Table 1 and is explained next.

Table 1. Initialization parameters of the GA.

Initial parameter	Details
<i>nChrom</i>	The size of the population, total number of chromosomes per generation
<i>maxGenerations</i>	The total number of generations
<i>initGeneProb</i>	The probability for a gene to have value "1" initially
<i>crossProb</i>	The probability of crossover
<i>mutProb</i>	The probability for mutation of each gene (uniform)
<i>nonUnf</i>	The mutation probability of the threshold(s) (non-uniform)
<i>thrGA_{min}</i>	Lower bound of the threshold(s) value
<i>thrGA_{max}</i>	Upper bound of the threshold(s) value
<i>bGA</i>	Freezing parameter
<i>predFactor</i>	Minimum number of samples with produced prediction

Step I An initial population of chromosomes is created. The chromosome is actually a vector, whose length is equal to the number of descriptors plus the number of similarity criteria used for defining neighbours of a target ENM. The threshold(s) are placed in specific positions in the chromosome representations. This creates hybrid chromosomes containing binary genes for descriptors and real genes for thresholds. A value of 1 means that the corresponding descriptor is selected for defining the distance matrix, while a value of 0 means that the descriptor has not been selected. The probability of a binary gene to be coded as 1 is denoted by *initGeneProb*. The real genes of the chromosomes contain the threshold values corresponding to the similarity criteria, and their values are selected randomly from the distance matrices of all samples, considering all variables in each group. In case only one similarity criterion is used, the threshold is placed at the end of the chromosome, whereas if two criteria are used, the thresholds are placed at the beginning and end of the chromosome.

Step II The fitness of each chromosome of the initial population is then calculated as follows:

- The Euclidean distances between all pairs of ENMs are computed using Eq. 23 for a single similarity criterion or Eqs. 24-25 for two similarity criteria.

$$dist_{i,j} = \sqrt{\sum_{\ell=1}^L attr_{\ell} (x_{i,\ell} - x_{j,\ell})^2}, \quad i = 1, \dots, N, \quad j = 1, \dots, N, \quad i \neq j \quad (\text{Eq. 23})$$

$$distA_{i,j} = \sqrt{\sum_{\ell=1}^{L_A} attrA_{\ell} (xA_{i,\ell} - xA_{j,\ell})^2}, i = 1, \dots, N, j = 1, \dots, N, i \neq j$$

(Eq. 24)

$$distB_{i,j} = \sqrt{\sum_{\ell=1}^{L_B} attrB_{\ell} (xB_{i,\ell} - xB_{j,\ell})^2}, i = 1, \dots, N, j = 1, \dots, N, i \neq j$$

(Eq. 25)

- For each ENM, neighbour ENMs are identified as the ones whose distance from the reference ENM is equal to, or lower than, the threshold value (in the case of two similarity criteria both distances should be equal to, or lower than, the respective thresholds).
- For ENMs without any neighbour, read-across predictions are not possible. The algorithm checks if Eq. 26 is satisfied, i.e. if ENMs with at least one neighbour are more than *predFactor* multiplied by the total number of ENMs. If yes, the algorithm proceeds with the next step. If not, the chromosome is rejected, and a new chromosome is generated as described in **Step I**.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N pred_i \geq predFactor \cdot N$$

(Eq. 26)

- The read-across predictions are computed using Eq. 27 for one similarity criterion or Eq. 28 for two similarity criteria) for ENMs with at least one neighbour.

$$\hat{y}_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^N y_j \cdot \frac{neib_{i,j}}{1+dist_{i,j}}}{\sum_{j=1}^N \frac{neib_{i,j}}{1+dist_{i,j}}}, \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$$

(Eq. 27)

$$\hat{y}_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^N y_j \cdot \frac{neib_{i,j}}{1+distA_{i,j}}}{\sum_{j=1}^N \frac{neib_{i,j}}{1+distA_{i,j}}}, \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$$

(Eq. 28)

- The MSE over all ENMs with at least one neighbor is computed using Eq. 29:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^N pred_i} \sum_{i=1}^n pred_i (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$$

(Eq. 29)

- The fitness function value of the chromosome is computed by Eq. 30. Score function has two components - the MSE term (better predictions lead to higher scores) and a regularization term, accompanied by a regularization factor *wfOF*, that controls the influence of the number of selected variables on the final score:

$$OF = MSE + wf_{OF} \cdot \sum_{\ell=1}^L attr_{\ell} \quad (\text{Eq. 30})$$

$$score = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } MSE = 0 \\ 1/OF & \text{if } MSE \neq 0 \end{cases}$$

- The chromosome with the highest (best) calculated fitness is saved for later analysis.

Step III A natural selection process takes place and is iterated *maxGenerations* times. During each iteration, the following procedure is repeated *nChrom/2* times and in total *nChrom* are selected that form the new generation.

- In order to ensure the reproduction of the fittest chromosomes, a "roulette wheel" approach is used. The method selects a pair of chromosomes from the previous population, based on randomly generated numbers that indicate the "slots" corresponding to the different chromosomes. The roulette wheel is constructed so that the size of each slot is proportional to the fitness of the corresponding chromosome. The roulette is "biased", thus chromosomes with a reproductive advantage (better fitness scores), have a higher probability of being selected. For each pair of selected chromosomes, the one with the highest score is saved as the *bestParent* for later use.
- The genetic operators of crossover are applied. According to the *crossProb* value, it is decided if the chromosomes are going to exchange strings of genes or not, in a randomly selected point that indicates the position of crossover.
- The genetic operator of mutation is applied. With probability *mutProb*, binary genes that correspond to a descriptor invert their value from 0 to 1 and vice versa, while non-uniform mutation is always performed to the threshold values.
- The two new chromosomes are evaluated with the procedure described in **Step II** and in case a chromosome does not meet the constraint defined by Eq. (26), it is replaced by its *bestParent*.

If the best chromosome of the previous generation is not included in the new generation, the algorithm places it in the position of the chromosome with the minimum score, in order to ensure that the chromosome with the best performance will always survive in the evolutionary procedure.

The best chromosome of the last generation is the result of the algorithm. The selected variables and threshold(s) corresponding to this chromosome will be used subsequently for read-across predictions of unknown ENMs. To evaluate the method, all the training examples are passed through step II described above to produce the read-across predictions.

The above steps are schematically described in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Schematic description of the proposed genetic algorithm.

Implementation of the method in the Apellis web application

Apellis, is a web-application, currently under development by NTUA using R and shiny, that implements the mathematical optimization problem approach described previously, through a user-friendly environment, which will be integrated into the NanoCommons infrastructure. The application currently supports a single threshold for defining neighbour ENMs.

Through **Apellis**, users can train a predictive model based on the concept of GAs, download it and use it to acquire predictions of a toxicity endpoint of interest. The application consists of two tabs for model development using one or two thresholds (similarity criteria) respectively and a “Help” tab. Each of the model development tabs consists of sub-tabs for training and use of the model:

- Read-across training: In this part, the user can train a predictive toxicity model through the GA workflow described previously (Varsou *et al.*, 2019a). An external validation approach is used to test the proposed read-across methodology, by dividing the full dataset into training and test subsets. This data partitioning can be achieved either by applying a random partition or a partition method (e.g. Kennard-Stone)(Daszykowski *et al.*, 2002). The training set is used in the GA workflow and determines the optimal set of descriptors and threshold(s) values. Using the read-across technique a table that contains all test ENMs with a successful prediction for the toxicity index is presented, a diagram of the test ENMs with their neighbours (Neighbours heatmap), as well as diagrams and tables containing information for the optimized parameters and model’s accuracy is produced.
 - Required specifications: This tab contains a series of operational parameters that should be tuned by the user concerning the evolutionary process and the objective function.
 - Probabilities: This tab contains all the necessary probability values that should be tuned for the evolutionary process.
- Obtaining predictions: In this part, the user can either use the trained model from the previous part, right after its’ development or he/she can upload and use a model that was trained and saved anytime, for the toxicity prediction of a set of ENMs with unknown toxicity index. After prediction a table that contains the predicted toxicity value for all the unknown ENMs is presented along with the ENMs neighbour diagram.

The Apellis application is demonstrated below, again using the dataset of Walkey *et al.* (2014).

Apellis: Read-across training

The user must upload one .csv file in the application containing the values of available descriptors and the values of the toxicity index, which will be predicted by the model. A demo dataset from Walkey *et al.* (2014) and filtered by Varsou *et al.* (2017) is provided. The user can select if the provided data should be normalized or not, the division method (Kennard-Stones or random) and the division ratio for validation purposes (training and test sets).

To continue the user must define a series of operational parameters of the GAs that are directly linked to the biological processes of selection, crossover and mutation of genes:

- Group of potential solutions (population): the number of chromosomes (an even number).
- Iterations (generations): the total number of cycles of selection, crossover and mutation between the potential solutions, leading to an optimal solution.
- The probability for each gene to have a value of 1 in the initial population.
- The probability of crossover (combination of two potential solutions).
- The probability for mutation of each gene (uniform mutation: the process of alteration of the crossed chromosomes. According to a predefined probability value, the procedure inverts the value of each gene: 0 becomes 1 and vice versa).
- The mutation probability of the threshold(s) (non-uniform mutation) and the freezing parameter for non-uniform mutation.

By pressing the training button, the model training begins. After the completion of training, a scatter plot containing the predicted and the actual values of all ENMs of the uploaded dataset (training and test sets) is presented. Users can zoom into specific areas of the plot, hover over the depicted points and compare the actual (experimental) and the predicted endpoint values. The diagram can be downloaded in .png format.

The experimental and the predicted endpoint values for the test ENMs with a successful prediction are also presented in the produced table entitled **Experimental vs. predicted endpoint values for the test set**. The prediction values have the same units as the actual values.

In addition, the app produces two tables, one containing the selected variables and one containing information about the trained model (optimized threshold, number of the generation that produced the best solution, the score, the total number of test samples with a successful prediction, the total number of selected variables and the q^2_{ext} statistic).

Finally, the app produces the ENMs' **Neighbours heatmap**, where the neighbours of the test ENMs in the training set are depicted. In this heatmap for each pair of training-test ENMs, a value of 1 (red) is allocated if these ENMs are neighbours, or a value of 0 (yellow) is allocated if these ENMs are not neighbours. The neighbours heat map actually gives a graphical representation of the ENMs grouping (grouping hypothesis).

Users can download all training results by clicking on **Download training results** in the form of a .zip file, containing .csv files with the selected variables, the neighbours for the test ENMs, the predictions for the test ENMs and all necessary statistics and model information.

Users can also name their model by typing in **Model title** and can download the trained model by clicking on **Download model** for future use in the following tab (**Obtain predictions**) which removes the need for constant training with the same data.

In the trained model presented in Figure 10, the scaled Walkey *et al.* (2014) dataset was divided into training and test subsets using the Kennard-Stone method in a ratio 75:25 (63 training and 21 test ENMs). Ten generations were used with ten chromosomes per generation. The developed model has an accuracy of 0.809 in external validation and produces predictions for all the test ENMs. The grouping hypothesis consists of the threshold value (1.553) and the 69 selected variables, also presented in the results.

D6.2 AOP-based grouping of ENMs

Figure 10. Apellis results after training with one similarity criteria, showing the experimental versus predicted endpoint values graphically and as a table, and the neighbours heatmap.

Apellis: Obtaining predictions

This section of the application can be used right after the read-across training or after the input of a model already trained by **Apellis**. In that way, the toxicity index of a data set of untested ENMs can be predicted, when all the descriptors that were used in training are known values. The user must upload a .csv file to the application containing the descriptor values for the untested dataset.

Grouping/Read-Across predictions using Piecewise Linear Optimization (PLA)

The third grouping/read-across methodology developed by NTUA is a modification and extension of the Optimal Piecewise Linear Regression Algorithm (OPLRA), proposed by Yang *et al.* (2016), for training robust and interpretable QSAR models. This method selects from the available features the one that best separates the sample domain into regions (partition feature) and produces multivariate linear equations that predict the available endpoint in each region. Cardoso-Silva *et al.* (2019) in their recent work with QSAR for small molecules have introduced OPLRA, a regularization parameter (OPLRAreg method) that has a twofold function; it controls overfitting and simultaneously selects the most important features for the endpoint prediction. Even though feature selection and domain segmentation are performed in an automated fashion, the user can control the level of regularization and the accuracy of the predictions through two parameters. The concept and the architecture of the algorithms fit perfectly to the requirements of read-across, because the OPLRAreg performs grouping of the available samples and applies an analogue approach for the endpoint prediction of ENMs belonging to each group. An advantage of OPLRAreg is that the grouping hypothesis is well-defined in terms of the partition feature, breakpoints and selected features in each region.

NTUA is currently working on an extension and adaptation of the OPLRAreg on nanotoxicity data, in order to automate the process of selecting an optimal read-across hypothesis, including feature selection and grouping of ENMs into regions. More specifically, the issue of multi-perspective characterisation of ENM (e.g. physicochemical, omics, quantum mechanical, image or biokinetics) is being addressed, by selecting the most important variable from each perspective and partitioning the ENMs into several groups in the hyper characterisation space. The method is being implemented in Matlab employing the free [YALMIP toolbox](#) for structuring and solving the Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) problems. The workflow of the algorithms is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Schematic description of the extended Piecewise Linear Programming grouping/read-across method

Figure 13 presents some preliminary results of the application of the method on the protein corona data of Walkey *et al.* (2014). The figure presents how ENMs are partitioned into two groups based on the PO4114 protein (Apolipoprotein B-100), which is identified as the most important variable. The linear equation defined in each region for predicting cellular association is also depicted in Figure 13.

D6.2 AOP-based grouping of ENMs

Figure 13. Extended OPLRAreg method, applied to the Walkey *et al.* (2014) dataset: Regions and distribution of samples (ENMs) in every region.

Enalos kNN read - across approach

The k -Nearest Neighbours (k NN) machine learning algorithm can be considered as a read-across strategy (Huluban *et al.*, 2016), as it requires experimental observations of only a few neighbours (similar ENMs) to the query ENM, in order to compute the endpoint prediction. The k NN methodology is a “lazy” learning technique, that classifies an instance based on the majority vote of the k closest training examples (neighbours). Where the endpoint has a numeric class, the prediction is the distance weighted average of the endpoint of the selected neighbours. An optimal k value is selected based on the calculated Euclidean distance between all instances and as weighting factors the inverse distances are used (Melagraki *et al.*, 2014, Witten *et al.*, 2016). In the case of a categorical endpoint each instance is assigned to the class indicated by the weighted majority vote of the k closest neighbours. Another important aspect of the analysis - apart from the simple endpoint prediction - is the possibility to observe the groups of k neighbours of each test ENM, and therefore to specify and map the analogous space, which is a prerequisite of the read-across framework (ECHA, 2015), and which can be used to support the justification of the read-across hypothesis.

NovaM has developed two read-across models based on the k NN machine learning algorithm: a Nanoinformatics Model for Zeta Potential Prediction and a Safe-by-Design Tool for Functionalized ENMs based on surface functionalised MWCNTs.

Safe-by-Design Tool for Functionalized ENMs

MWCNTs are currently used in numerous industrial applications and products, therefore fast and accurate evaluation of their biological and toxicological effects is of utmost importance. Computational methods and techniques, previously applied in the area of cheminformatics for the prediction of adverse effects of chemicals, can also be applied in the case of ENMs, in an effort to reduce expensive and time-consuming experimental procedures.

In this context, a validated and predictive nanoinformatics model has been developed for the accurate prediction of the biological (carbonic anhydrase binding) and toxicological profile (cytotoxicity) of decorated MWCNTs based only on the structure of the decorating molecules (Varsou *et al.*, 2019b). The nanoinformatics workflow was fully validated according to the OECD principles before it was released online via the Enalos Cloud platform³. The web-service is a ready-to-use, user-friendly application whose purpose is to facilitate decision making, as part of a safe-by-design framework for novel carbon nanotubes. Thus, it represents a useful tool within a safety-by-design framework and can contribute to the reduction of *in vivo* experiments and their replacement by *in vitro* and in due course only *in silico* experiments.

To initiate a prediction, the user must provide one or several structures of compounds being considered as potential decorating molecules for MWCNTs and gets, within seconds, the prediction of the Carbonic Anhydrase II (HCAII) binding and their toxicity profile, along with a warning on the reliability of the predictions based on the models' domain of applicability limits. For this purpose, the

³ <http://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/CNT/>

platform provides three different options for inserting the required data to the model (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Enalos Nanoinformatics Cloud platform user-friendly interface. At the left-handed side the molecular drawing tool is found. At the top right-handed the SMILES input form can be seen followed by the option of importing a .sdf file.

- For only one entry: The user can draw the molecular structure of interest using the drawing tool. When using the drawing tool, only one structure can be submitted at a time. The user can easily select from the different panels' specific atoms, bonds or substructures and then construct the decorating molecule.
- For multiple entries: The user can enter the SMILES notation of one or several structures separated by newlines or he/she can select and import a .sdf file with several structures.

When structures are uploaded in either way, a prediction is generated (usually within seconds) by clicking the Execute button of the corresponding field. When properties are uploaded for a set of decorating molecules, a prediction is generated by submitting the input structures, the predictive model is then applied to the data provided and the output is generated.

The results include the predicted HCAII binding class ("binder"/"non-binder") to the MWCNTs and the toxicity class ("toxic"/"non-toxic") of the resultant decorated-MWCNTs for each structure entered, and an indication of whether this prediction could be considered reliable based on the domain of applicability of the model (Figure 15). By clicking the Download files button, the above table is downloaded in both .csv and .html format. In the produced .csv files, the interested users can observe the neighbours of the training set used for the prediction of each one of the input samples.

[Download files](#)

Safe-by-Design: Functionalised Nanomaterials

Knime report powered by Birt

"Toxicity"	"Domain (Toxicity)"	"Activity"	"Domain (Activity)"
toxic	reliable	non-binder	reliable
non-toxic	reliable	binder	reliable
toxic	reliable	non-binder	reliable
toxic	unreliable	binder	reliable

Date: Apr 2, 2019 5:43 PM

Author: NovaMechanics Ltd

1 of 1

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Figure 15. Results table. The first and the third columns contain the prediction for each input sample and the second and fourth columns contain the reliability of the corresponding prediction according to the domain of applicability.

Nanoinformatics Model for Zeta Potential Prediction

A read-across predictive model was developed for zeta-potential of ENMs and released through the NanoCommons platform as an online application. Based on the ENM core type, main elongation and pH value, users interested in ENM design can import different ENM datasets and study the effects of different inputs on the zeta-potential value, a decisive step during the design process of novel ENMs. Users can use an image analysis tool of their choice or the provided Enalos NanoXtract tool (<http://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/NanoXtract/>), to provide the requested image nanodescriptor (main elongation). The results produced include the predicted zeta-potential values for each ENM sample as well as a warning on the prediction reliability according to the domain of applicability limits. The neighbours of each ENM in the training set are also available through the web-service.

To initiate a prediction, the user must indicate the type of core of the ENMs and the pH of the solution where the experimental measurement of the zeta potential would have been made. In addition, the user must provide the value of the main elongation of the ENMs. Main elongation is an image descriptor that can be calculated from TEM images using the Enalos NanoXtract tool or another image analysis tool of interest (e.g. ImageJ). The user has two alternative ways to provide the above information - either by completing the provided form or by importing a .csv file, as shown in Figure 16.

Nanoinformatics Model for Zeta Potential Prediction Powered by Enalos Cloud Platform

[User Guide](#)

Row ID	Type of core	pH	Main Elongation
1	oxide	6.5	
2	oxide	6.5	
3	oxide	6.5	
4	oxide	6.5	
5	oxide	6.5	
6	oxide	6.5	
7	oxide	6.5	
8	oxide	6.5	
9	oxide	6.5	
10	oxide	6.5	
11	oxide	6.5	
12	oxide	6.5	
13	oxide	6.5	
14	oxide	6.5	
15	oxide	6.5	
16	oxide	6.5	
17	oxide	6.5	
18	oxide	6.5	
19	oxide	6.5	
20	oxide	6.5	

Execute computations Reset

Upload csv file CSV title Download template file

Execute computations Reset

Figure 16. Enalos Zeta Potential Prediction platform. At the top page the input form can be seen and at the bottom by clicking on Upload csv file button, the user can import a .csv file with all the required properties.

- For only one entry: Each row corresponds to one ENM. The user selects from the first drop-down menu the type of core of the ENM (pure metal/metal oxide) and from the second the pH value (6.5/7) of the medium of interest. Finally, the user enters a numerical value of the main elongation between 0 and 1.
- For multiple entries: Each row corresponds to a different ENM. The user provides information as above and now fills in data for multiple rows each corresponding to one ENM. For one ENM or for a set of ENMs, all necessary information can be submitted via a .csv file.

By clicking the **Execute computation** button found under the online form or under the imported .csv file, depending on the method chosen to provide the input data, predictions for each ENM are generated.

A table is presented with the produced results. The “Predicted zeta potential [mV]” column contains the zeta potential prediction in mV of each submitted ENM, based on the predictive model. The “Reliability” column contains an indication on the reliability of predictions based on the model’s domain of applicability limits (Figure 17).

Download files

Row ID	Predicted zeta potential [mV]	Reliability
"IO166E Gold 12 nm PEG-OH"	-0.5815616505801628	"reliable"
"AgNPs PEG 10nm"	-23.554501736363807	"reliable"
"AgNPs PEG 20nm"	-27.79291401386539	"unreliable"
"AgNPs PVP 7nm"	-29.631770892835036	"reliable"
"TiO2 103"	23.107595387224467	"reliable"
"prom ZnO"	18.615889644766884	"reliable"
"Ce NM 211"	38.20268062475627	"reliable"
"S40"	-28.832095935920286	"reliable"
"IO003"	-10.691819408446678	"unreliable"

Figure 17. Generated output page. The first column of the results table contains the prediction for each input ENM and the second column contains the reliability of each prediction based on the model's domain of applicability. This table can also be downloaded in .csv and .html format by clicking in the corresponding button.

By clicking the Download files button, the above table is downloaded in .csv format. In the downloaded files the neighbours of each ENM in the training set can be also found.

Similarity tools in GUIDEnano

This section presents the sophisticated and systematic method for ENM similarity assessment, which has been developed as part of the GUIDEnano tool and is now implemented and integrated into NanoCommons. This strategy overcomes the scarcity of ENM hazard reference values, by approximating them using existing data from literature sources and applying a similarity quantification methodology between the relevant toxicology studies that are already published.

Similarity module in GUIDEnano

GUIDEnano is an interactive web-based guidance tool that aims to guide ENM producers and nano-enabled product manufacturers in the risk assessment of their nano-enabled products, and the identification of suitable risk mitigation measures. The GUIDEnano tool was initially developed during the [GUIDEnano](#) project funded under the EU Seventh Framework program (2013 – 2017), and it is currently further developed under the framework of other ongoing EU funded projects (caLIBRAte, GRACIOUS and NanoCommons). The tool combines a range of predictive models, multi-level decision trees, and databases to derive critical information along with the risk assessment and risk mitigation processes (Figure 18). The user has total flexibility to define the scope of the assessment, ranging from a single activity to a collection of connected activities throughout the life-cycle of a nano-enabled product (i.e. from production to waste management). To perform the risk assessment, the user is directed towards a series of interconnected modules including ENMs, activities, compartments/fate, exposure, hazard and risk assessment. To complete the ultimate risk assessment and obtain the risk coefficient ratio, the user needs to input into the hazard module a final safety limit value (FSLV) for the specific ENM and hazard endpoint considered.

Since the FSLV is not always available, a similarity module was developed to help the users in selecting the adequate studies by including quantitative criteria to evaluate their quality and relevance (Fernandez-Cruz et al. 2018) and considering the similarity of the ENM used in the hazard study with the 'exposure relevant ENM'.

Figure 18. GUIDEnano Framework to assess the acceptability of a study for extrapolating toxicity data between two ENMs.

The ENM similarity approach uses the current knowledge on relationships between ENM physicochemical properties and their corresponding hazards. For ENMs, a specific property can be expected to affect one hazard endpoint differently in comparison to another. As a reference, a change in ENM shape from spherical to fiber may increase the inhalation toxicity but may not influence dermal or oral toxicity. As presented in Table 2, ENM physicochemical properties such as chemical composition, impurities, crystalline form, aggregate size, particle size are considered relevant for oral and dermal exposure, whilst properties such as shape and density are more significant for inhalation exposure. Scientific justification on which ENM physicochemical properties are selected for each exposure route is detailed elsewhere (Park *et al.*, 2018).

Table 2. The physicochemical properties included and excluded from the GUIDEnano similarity tools. Some ENM physicochemical properties are excluded because the precise methodology is missing and/or is taken into consideration in other physicochemical properties. # Note that impurities physicochemical property is specifically applied to CNTs.

Physicochemical property	Route of exposure
Chemical composition	Oral, dermal and Inhalation
Crystalline form	Oral, dermal and Inhalation
Impurities#	Oral, dermal and Inhalation
Aggregate size	Oral, dermal and Inhalation
Surface chemistry	Not included*
Particle size/range	Oral, dermal and Inhalation
Density	Inhalation
Shape	Inhalation
Surface area	Not included*
Solubility/dissolution	Not included*
Hydrophobicity	Not included*
Zeta potential/surface charge	Not included*
Dispersability	Not included*
Dustiness	Not included*
Biological (re)activity	Not included*
Photoreactivity	Not included*

For each physicochemical property, a specific algorithm has been developed to obtain a score between 0 and 1, where 1 means similar and 0 not similar. From the similarity score of each relevant property, an overall similarity score is obtained as described below. In the following paragraphs some examples of the developed algorithm for crystallinity and particle size/range are reported.

Crystallinity: The algorithm uses quantitative analysis of X-Ray Diffraction data. It compares the weight percentages (wt.%) of each crystalline form present in each of the materials, and takes a sum of the overlaps in wt.% for all crystalline forms to derive a similarity score as described below.

$$S_{Crystallinity} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \min(C_i^A, C_i^B)}{100} \quad (\text{Eq. 31})$$

where k is the number of crystalline forms present in any of the two ENMs under comparison, min denotes minimum value, and C_i^A and C_i^B denote the % of crystalline form in materials A and B, respectively.

Particle size/range: To allow the similarity assessment of the full-size distributions of two ENMs, the ratios of multiple size percentiles (i.e. P10, P20, P30, P40, P50, P60, P70, P80, and P90) of two materials, obtained from the same equipment and method, are calculated as follows:

$$S_{size}(X^{th}) = \frac{\min(X_a^{th}, X_b^{th})}{\max(X_a^{th}, X_b^{th})} \quad (\text{Eq. 32})$$

where X^{th} is the x-percentile of the number- or mass-based size distribution under consideration (a or b), and x is in the set {10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90}. Then, the similarity score is calculated as the geometric mean of all percentile ratios:

$$S_{size} = \text{Geometric mean}(S_{size}(X^{th})) \quad (\text{Eq. 33})$$

where the geometric mean is taken over all values of x in the set {10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90}. The size similarity assessment can be done on both mass- and particle number-based size distributions, as long as the same unit is used for both ENMs.

Overall similarity score:

The determination of a similarity score is a challenging aspect due to the lack of uniform characterization methods, the variation of ENM properties within the same ENM batch and the dynamic nature of ENM properties, among others. In addition, no method exists to establish thresholds for distinguishing between similar and dissimilar materials. In the GUIDEnano tool, two ENM are considered similar enough to extrapolate hazard data from as long as the similarity factor is greater than or equal to 0.3.

Case Study:

To illustrate the ENM similarity approach, a case study previously developed in Park *et al.* (2018) is presented hereafter. The case study assesses the similarity between a TiO₂-Case and three different TiO₂ ENMs called TiO₂-M, TiO₂-F and TiO₂-UF (see Table 3) described previously (Oberdörster *et al.*, 1994, Ma-Hock *et al.*, 2009) in the context of worker exposure through inhalation when handling the TiO₂ dry powder.

Table 3. Physicochemical data used in the case study, extracted from Park *et al.* (2018).

Material	TiO ₂ -case	Ma-Hock et al. (2009); Lowest tested concentration (TiO ₂ -M)	Oberdorster, Ferin, and Lehnert (1994); Fine (TiO ₂ -F)	Oberdorster, Ferin, and Lehnert (1994); Ultrafine (TiO ₂ -UF)
Chemical composition	TiO ₂	TiO ₂	TiO ₂	TiO ₂
Crystalline form	>99% anatase	14% rutile - 86% anatase	100% anatase	100% anatase
Density	3.8 g/cm ³	4.2 g/cm ³	3.8 g/cm ³	3.8 g/cm ³
Primary size	7.5 ± 1.5 nm	25.1 ± 8.2 nm	250 nm	20 nm
Aggregate size	1.5 μm/GSD: 2.0	1.1 μm/GSD: 2.3	0.78 μm/GSD: 1.7	0.71 μm/GSD: 1.7
Shape	Spherical	Spherical	Spherical	Spherical

GSD: geometric standard deviation.

- **Chemical composition:** The four TiO₂ nanoforms are uncoated and have the same core composition, the similarity score for the chemical composition is 1.
- **Crystallinity:** As the TiO₂-case, TiO₂-UF and TiO₂-F are anatase (up to 99%), their similarity score is 1. TiO₂-M is composed of 86% anatase and 14% rutile. As described previously the similarity score $S = (86 + 0)/100 = 0.86$.

- **Primary size:** In this case study authors assumed a normal particle size distribution centered at the listed primary size value (7.5; 25.1; 250 and 20 nm for TiO₂-case, TiO₂-M, TiO₂-F, and TiO₂-UF, respectively) and a 20 % standard deviation (when SD is absent). The calculated similarities of TiO₂-case with TiO₂-M, TiO₂-F and TiO₂-UF are 0.31, 0.03 and 0.38, respectively.
- **Aggregate/agglomerate size:** The mean and standard deviation was used to describe the aggregate/agglomerate size. Considering this data the similarity score is 0.73, 0.52 and 0.47, for the TiO₂-case with TiO₂-M, TiO₂-F, and TiO₂-UF, respectively.
- **Density:** The similarity score for density is 1, except for TiO₂-M that indicates a density of 4.2 g/cm³. Here the similarity score is calculated as 1 for TiO₂-M and TiO₂-F and at 0.98 for TiO₂-UF, respectively.
- **Shape:** A similarity score of 1 is attributed to all three NFs since they are all spherical.

Table 4. Compilation of similarity results from the TiO₂ case study (Park et al., 2018)

Comparison of TiO ₂ -case versus	TiO ₂ -M	TiO ₂ -F	TiO ₂ -UF
Chemical composition	1	1	1
Crystalline form	0.86	1	1
Primary size	0.31	0.03	0.38
Aggregate size	0.73	0.52	0.47
Density	0.98	1	1
Shape	1	1	1
Overall	0.31	0.03	0.38

All similarity scores for each ENM property are summarised in Table 4. The overall similarity score (relative to the TiO₂-case ENM) corresponds to 0.31, 0.03 and 0.38 for TiO₂-M, TiO₂-F, and TiO₂-UF, respectively, meaning that according to GUIDEnano methodology the TiO₂-M and TiO₂-UF hazard data can be used with an uncertainty factor of $1/0.31 = 3.2$ and $1/0.38 = 2.6$, respectively. For inhalation, the lowest observed adverse effect level (LOAEL) identified for TiO₂-M was 2 g/m³ which is corrected for the dissimilarity factor to be $2/3.2 = 0.62$ mg/m³.

This approach highlights criteria and possible quantitative methods to evaluate the similarity between ENMs based on commonly available ENM physicochemical properties and provides a way forward in the current conceptual discussions on reading across from well-studied ENMs to less studied variants and potentially even to other ENM compositions.

Supervised Learning in ENM Grouping:

This section presents the Random Forest (RF) classification method, which was used for supervised learning in support of the ENM grouping framework, developed during the NanoReg2 project. RFs build up a number of decision trees based on bootstrap samples of the original data. Within each decision tree, the input variables, here the ENM physicochemical properties, are combined in such a way that they separate both classes from each other as well as possible. In this step, another layer of randomness is added by considering only a subset of the input variables as potential split criteria for each split. Which descriptor is finally chosen to set the split criterion depends on their separation performance. Common choices to select the split criterion are the Gini impurity or the prediction accuracy (also called permutation error) (Breiman, 2003). Both criteria are described in more detail below in the paragraph on [Recursive Feature Elimination \(RFE\)](#). In order to assess the generalizability of the constructed RF, the dataset should be divided into a training set, which is used to build the RF and a test set, which is used to assess how well the RF performs on a set of data that the RF has not seen before. Here, we used cross-validation in a leave-one-out manner. Thus, for each ENM, the class label was predicted by the RF generated on all other ENMs. The final prediction of toxicity for the test ENM is based on a majority voting of all trees in the RF. As here RF classification is used, the outcome variable holds class labels for each sample.

Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) in Random Forest Classification

For reduction of the number of input variables of the RF, backward RFE (Guyon *et al.*, 2002) is applied, based on the mean decrease of accuracy (MDA) importance. The MDA is computed by randomly permuting the values of each input variable, one at a time, and assessing how much the prediction accuracy drops by doing so. Larger decreases in the prediction accuracy correspond to higher importance of the input variable under consideration. The feature with the minimum value for MDA, corresponding to the least important variable was removed from the input set and a new RF was built based on this reduced set of variables. The minimal set of input variables giving an optimal balanced accuracy was determined. Similarly, RFE was performed based on the Gini importance as the variable exclusion criterion. Gini importance measures how well the samples can be assigned to the two output classes by making a split on the variable under consideration at a specific node. The higher that value is, the better is the separation of the instances into the two classes and the higher is the importance of the inspected feature. Means and standard deviations for the MDA, as well as Gini importance values for each feature, were calculated in order to infer knowledge on the importance of each ENM physico-chemical property on the toxicity outcome. Variability estimates of the Gini importance result from the leave-one-out cross-validation, in which variable importance was assessed within each RF model and then averaged across all models, were determined.

The performance of the classification models was assessed based on the number of correct and incorrect class predictions. Briefly, each ENM was assigned a class label (active/passive) based on the results of, in this case, two previously performed studies: 1) rat short-term inhalation studies (STIS) (Landsiedel *et al.*, 2014) or, 2) a macrophage assay (Wiemann *et al.*, 2016) (Table 6 -- True class). A material is correctly classified if the class predicted (Table 6 -- Predicted class) by the model is the

same as the label that the ENM was originally assigned. Sensitivity (true predictions as 'active' (true positives)/all predictions as 'active' (positives)), specificity (true predictions as 'passive' (true negatives)/all predictions as 'passive' (negatives)) and balanced accuracy (sensitivity+specificity/2) were assessed by comparing the assigned class label to the predicted one.

The implementation of RFs from the R package 'randomForest' was used, with the number of trees generated being set to 5,000 and the number of features assessed at each split being set to the default value. An R package implementing the methods presented here is available at https://github.com/AileenBahl/ML_Tox.

Supervised learning approach - Random forest

Full model

The method was applied to the set of ENM shown in Table 6 for which the physicochemical descriptors depicted in Table 5 are known. The heatmap of physico-chemical properties across ENMs is depicted in Figure 19. As a starting point, a full RF model was created by incorporating all assessed physico-chemical properties as input variables. This leads to a correct prediction of the toxicity of six ENMs and a misclassification of five ENM. The sensitivity of that classifier is 0.4, the specificity is 0.67 and the balanced accuracy is 0.54. The stability of the correct predictions as assessed by the ratio between the correct and the incorrect votes is roughly the same as compared to the stability of the incorrect predictions.

The importance of each input variable in that RF is assessed as the MDA or mean decrease in Gini importance, respectively (see Figure 20 and Table 5). In both cases, zeta potential, dissolution rate, surface-based ESR DMPO (i.e. electron spin resonance measurement of 5,5-dimethyl-1-pyrroline-N-oxide), and redox potential are among the top 5 highest-ranking variables. For Gini importance the set of top 5 variables is completed by mass-based ESR CPH (1-hydroxy-3-carboxy-2, 2, 5, 5-tetramethylpyrrolidine), while for accuracy it is the relative density.

Reduced models

As the performance of RFs is drastically reduced if a lot of noise variables, not highly related to the outcome variable, are included in the prediction, the number of input variables was reduced to see whether the performance of the predictor could be improved. We assessed backward RFE based on MDA as well as on Gini importance prior to the actual model building step.

First, the number of input variables in the model was reduced based on the MDA with re-evaluation. In each step of the RFE, a RF was built, the input variables were ranked according to their MDA, and the variable with the lowest importance was removed, and a new RF based on this reduced set of input variables was created. The minimal set of input variables leading to the highest balanced accuracy of the model was then determined.

The best model was obtained using zeta potential, dissolution rate and redox potential. In that case,

only two ENMs were misclassified (SiO₂_15_Phospho and TiO₂ NM-105) leading to a sensitivity of 0.8, a specificity of 0.83 and a balanced accuracy of 0.82. The empirical frequencies of votes for both classes in the prediction of SiO₂_15_Phospho were almost equal (55% of all votes for 'active' and 45% of all votes for 'passive') and the difference in the number of correct and incorrect votes was much smaller than for most other ENMs (exceptions: SiO₂_15_unmod and CuPhthalocyanine Green which also had almost equally many votes for either of the classes, see Table 6). However, in the case of TiO₂ NM-105, the prediction of the incorrect class label is rather stable (85% of all votes suggested 'passive' as the correct class label). The variable importance for the zeta potential is 20.50 ± 7.11 , for dissolution rate it is 16.49 ± 5.59 and for redox potential it is 15.28 ± 3.88 . The spatial distribution of ENMs across the space spanned by the three variables is depicted in Figure 21.

Using the mean decrease in Gini importance instead of the mean decrease in accuracy to rank the features, the balanced accuracy of the model drops to 0.73 with SiO₂_15_unmod being misclassified in addition to the previous two materials. The empirical frequencies of votes do not improve and the surface-based ESR measurement with the DMPO spin trap is needed in addition to the 3 parameters from the model based on the MDA. Thus, the MDA model leads to better results in that case.

Discussion

Independent of uncertainties in the results, this study was able to show how machine learning and feature selection strategies can be used for linking physico-chemical properties of ENMs to their toxicity. These extracted physico-chemical properties may then be used to detect ENMs which are similar in terms of their toxicity effect, i.e. for establishing grouping with respect to ENM hazards. Here, we used a categorization into active and passive materials in accordance with previous studies (Wiemann *et al.*, 2016, Landsiedel *et al.*, 2014). However, the prediction algorithm may be extended to the case of multiple class labels or even continuous outcomes once a larger number of consistent data is collected. A better understanding of which of the many possible ENM physico-chemical properties actually drive toxicity will certainly enable the selection of sufficiently similar ENMs to achieve robust grouping. The properties and models developed here should be regarded as a first basis for how to further develop ENM grouping procedures and how to better understand and interpret similarity between ENM variants. Further refinement of the models and external validation with more and different ENMs will be necessary to obtain reliable predictions and resolve the misclassifications presented here. Multiple improvement strategies will be tested in our future work.

As not all misclassifications have been resolved yet, the predictors included in our dataset do not seem to be sufficient to explain completely the underlying differences in mechanisms of toxicity. Thus, additional variables may have to be included in the model building step to improve the prediction accuracy. Therefore, in future we are planning to extend our set of input parameters by adding more computed theoretical descriptors (Haase and Klaessig, 2018, [DRAGON 7.0](#), [MOPAC2016](#)), as well as descriptors based on protein coronas and multi-omics data. Furthermore, we are specifically searching for similar data sets that might be helpful for data integration and external validation of our model. Furthermore, we will also include ENM descriptors measured in relevant media or bio-fluids.

D6.2 AOP-based grouping of ENMs

Figure 19: Heatmap of physico-chemical properties across ENMs. The table of physico-chemical properties were translated into colors ranging from dark blue for the smallest values to dark red for the highest values. All properties were scaled across ENMs in order to make them comparable and avoid overrepresentation of those properties having larger values in general in the clustering step. The black labels on the left side of the x-axis correspond to the active ENMs, the purple ones on the right side correspond to passive ENMs. Comparing both sides shows that none of the physico-chemical properties alone is able to separate active from passive ENMs. The dendrogram shows the similarity of the physico-chemical properties across all studied ENMs. The length of the branches indicates how closely correlated the properties are. Shorter branches represent higher similarity and thus higher correlation.

Figure 20. Variable importance of each parameter within the full RF model. a) Mean decrease in accuracy and b) mean decrease in Gini importance are depicted for each physico-chemical property. Properties at the top of the plot are of highest importance in the particular model.

D6.2 AOP-based grouping of ENMs

Table 5: Variable importance values in the full RF model. Means and standard deviations for the mean decrease of accuracy (MDA) as well as Gini importance values for each feature are given. Standard deviations result from the leave-one-out cross-validation, in which variable importance was assessed within each RF model and then averaged across all models.

Physico-chemical parameter	Mean decrease in accuracy	Mean decrease in Gini importance
Dissolution rate	11.83 ± 3.18	0.45 ± 0.12
Zeta potential	9.66 ± 5.28	0.72 ± 0.12
Relative density	6.44 ± 2.25	0.23 ± 0.07
Redox potential	6.00 ± 2.96	0.38 ± 0.09
ESR DMPO (surface-based)	0.94 ± 3.41	0.39 ± 0.06
Band gap	-0.24 ± 4.85	0.23 ± 0.09
ESR CPH (surface-based)	-0.54 ± 2.89	0.28 ± 0.05
Hydrodynamic diameter	-1.51 ± 4.29	0.30 ± 0.07
ESR CPH (mass-based)	-2.19 ± 5.03	0.40 ± 0.13
Surface area	-2.41 ± 3.48	0.23 ± 0.06
Isoelectric point	-3.65 ± 4.65	0.36 ± 0.09
Primary particle size	-4.42 ± 3.32	0.26 ± 0.04
ESR DMPO (mass-based)	-6.32 ± 1.73	0.21 ± 0.03

D6.2 AOP-based grouping of ENMs

Table 6: Classification result for the reduced Random Forest (RF) model based after backward RFE. The input parameters, comprised of the physico-chemical properties in this case, were reduced in a stepwise manner removing the most unimportant feature in each step. RFs were sequentially built on these reduced sets of input parameters. The RF with the best balanced accuracy and the minimal number of input features was selected as the final model. Internal model validation was performed using leave-one-out cross-validation. The best model was obtained with the three physico-chemical properties zeta potential, dissolution rate and redox potential as input parameters and variable importance being addressed by the MDA. Results for this model are shown in this table.

NM	True class	Predicted Class	Empirical frequency of votes for label 'active'	'Empirical frequency of votes for label 'passive'
SiO ₂ _15_unmod	Active	Active	0.56	0.44
SiO ₂ _15_Amino	Passive	Passive	0.24	0.76
SiO ₂ _15_Phospho	Passive	Active	0.55	0.45
SiO ₂ _40	Active	Active	0.82	0.18
SiO ₂ _7	Active	Active	0.74	0.26
SiO ₂ _7_TMS2	Passive	Passive	0.13	0.87
SiO ₂ _7_TMS3	Passive	Passive	0.20	0.80
CuPhthalocyanine Blue	Passive	Passive	0.31	0.69
CuPhthalocyanine Green	Passive	Passive	0.43	0.57
TiO ₂ NM-105	Active	Passive	0.15	0.85
Mn ₂ O ₃	Active	Active	0.81	0.19

Random forest with three input parameters

Figure 21: Scatterplot of the input variables of the RF model reduced by RFE. The best RF model after RFE contains only three of the physico-chemical properties as input properties: zeta potential, redox potential and dissolution rate. Their mean values for each ENM are shown here.

ENM Grouping based on application of the BMD method to AOPs

This section presents a workflow for ENM grouping, developed by NTUA, which combines the concept of AOPs with the Benchmark Dose (BMD) dose-response method for calculating points of departure (POD)s, which are useful for risk assessment. The method is applied on data derived from high-throughput molecular techniques, which extract the different responses at the gene level, capturing in detail the effects of the exposure to a variety of ENMs. We present first the important components of the method, which is followed by a presentation of the complete workflow. This subsection ends with a case study, presenting the application of the method on grouping ENMs with respect to AOP 173 - Inflammation mediated lung fibrosis (<https://aopwiki.org/aops/173>).

Toxicogenomics Analysis

Whole genome gene expression profiling techniques allow for the simultaneous analysis of changes in the expression of all the genes in a sample that are caused by the exposure to an ENM. Bioinformatics analysis of transcriptomics data offers a genome wide collection of gene expression patterns, in the form of differentially expressed gene lists, that can be further analyzed to uncover the biological processes and signaling and metabolic pathways that are affected due to the exposure. These can, in turn, reveal the actual mechanisms of toxicity induced by the exposure to ENMs.

In standard toxicogenomics analyses, gene expression data are used to extract information about the association between chemicals, genes and diseases, as well as to identify the mechanisms that lead to the pathophysiological changes causing the pathological phenotypes. For bulk chemicals, it has been proven that substances that belong to a common class, based on a set of criteria, induce similar patterns of gene expression and cause similar toxicity, thus transcriptomics are useful in identifying the distinct chemical categories or for classifying the compounds (Hamadeh *et al.*, 2002).

Also, several studies that describe the implementation of whole genome gene expression profiling methods coupled with powerful computational tools and bioinformatics analysis workflows on model organism samples, such as *M. musculus*, to study specific ENMs toxicity have been published in the past. For example, Husein *et al.* (2013) and Halapannavar *et al.* (2015) studied the ENM properties that lead to the manifestation of pulmonary response and shed light on the molecular mechanisms that cause tissue damage following exposure to nano-titanium dioxide particles (nanoTiO₂).

Other studies have reported the toxicogenomic profiles that are caused by the exposure to carbon black ENMs, and various MWCNTs (Bourdon *et al.*, 2012, Poulsen *et al.*, 2013, Poulsen *et al.*, 2015). Their common ground is that regardless of the class of the ENM under investigation, the same molecular perturbations at the gene expression and pathway level after exposure to ENMs lead to the same, common pathophysiological phenotype, namely lung inflammation, although the severity of the effect reflected in the number of genes and the respective intensity (fold-change) is different. A few studies have also concluded that gene expression data can be used to predict the potency of ENMs to cause a set of diseases before the phenotype is established, highlighting their usefulness to prioritize ENMs for further investigation (Williams & Halapannavar, 2016, Nikota *et al.*, 2016, Labib *et al.*, 2016).

AOP activation due to exposure to ENMs

Lately, there is increasing interest in using omics approaches and data to develop AOPs, relate exposure to ENMs with activation of AOPs and provide useful insight for hazard estimation. Labib *et al.* (2016) used transcriptomics to propose new AOPs, while Brockmeier *et al.* (2017) used already described AOPs with transcriptomics data analysis. In turn, knowledge on AOPs can support read-across and grouping methods and support human risk assessment by relevance to apical endpoints.

For AOPs to be pertinent to hazard and risk assessment, quantitative measurements are required. MIEs or other KEs, assuming that species and dose-level specificity are taken into account, are useful to establish a threshold for an apical effect. Many studies have already shown that the global changes in gene expression that accompany ENM exposure are associated with the development of molecular phenotypes in a dose-dependent manner (Halappanavar *et al.*, 2015).

Benchmark Dose (BMD) method for modelling dose-response data

BMD is defined as a dose (or concentration) of a substance that corresponds to a low but measurable change in response, namely the benchmark response (BMR), which is predetermined to be above or below the response observed in the control samples. Due to inherent limitations of the No Observed Adverse Effect Level (NOAEL) / Lowest Observed Adverse Effect Level (LOAEL) approach, the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and the Joint FAO/WHO Expert Committee on Food Additives (JECFA) favor the use of the BMD approach for deriving the point of departure (POD), also named Reference Point (RP), to calculate the margins of exposure (MOE), which are safe or acceptable, for substances that are both genotoxic and carcinogenic. The BMD method takes into account the whole dose-response curve and permits the calculation of the lower and the upper bounds of the BMD, denoted BMDL and BMDU respectively. In practice, the lower confidence limit of BMD, namely the BMDL, is used for regulatory purposes as it is the most conservative estimate (more detailed information on the BMD method and comparison with NOAEL methods was provided in NanoCommons deliverable report D6.1).

BMD analysis can be extended to incorporate the dose-response information related to the gene or pathway perturbations that follow ENM exposure (Thomas *et al.*, 2007, 2011, 2013). For instance, it can be implemented to identify the doses that lead to a significant change in the gene or pathway response in comparison to control samples. The results from studies that followed this concept have revealed the agreement between the transcriptional/pathway BMDs and the standard apical endpoint BMDs. For this reason, the transcriptional/pathway BMDs can be used to estimate PODs for ENM-induced toxicity for risk assessment as well as to group ENMs according to their power to induce toxicity-related phenotypes AOPs (Halappanavar *et al.*, 2019).

Workflow description

The input to the NanoCommons BMD workflow is a whole genome expression dataset for multiple doses. The workflow consists of three parts. The first part applies a comprehensive toxicogenomics analysis to the data and identifies the genes that have been over or under expressed due to exposure to the ENM and a list of the affected pathways using multiple pathway ontologies and databases. The second part applies the BMD method to each one of the differentially expressed genes identified in the first step and computes the BMD metric for each gene. The last part combines the results of the second part to compute BMD metrics for pathways or AOPs. The detailed presentation of the workflow follows next:

WORKFLOW Input: whole genome expression data

A. Toxicogenomics analysis using Bioinformatics

Note: Acute/subacute/chronic exposure related data can be included in the analysis depending on the phenotype of interest

- Input: publicly available data from the Gene Expression Omnibus (**GEO**) database, downloaded using the function `getGEO` of '**GEOquery**' R/Bioconductor library. The dataset includes the normalized, \log_2 transformed relative intensities and the study design information.
- '**Limma**' linear modeling, using the dose and treatment as fixed effects variables, and the \log_2 relative intensities as the dependent variable:
 - a. False discovery Rate (FDR) multiple testing correction at $\alpha = 0.05$
 - b. Gene selection criteria : $|\text{FoldChange (FC)}| > 0.5$ & $\text{FDR} < 0.05$
- **Functional Pathway Analysis:** using Library 'enrichR' R/Cran
- Output: one **differentially expressed gene (DEG) list** per ENM type and the **corresponding affected pathways/functions** (one list for each ontology/database per ENM type).

B. Pathway BMD response modelling:

- Input: ENM exposure doses ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mouse}$), the downloaded normalized \log_2 intensities
- The R/Cran libraries 'bmd' for **Benchmark dose analysis** for dose-response data, 'drc' for **Analysis of Dose-Response Curves** were used
- Calculation of **Median pathway BMD** for which pathways gene sets were altered:
 - a. The \log_2 intensities corresponding to the common differentially expressed genes were centered using the mean of the control samples;
 - b. Model fitting using the `bmd` function of 'bmd' R/Cran library, setting a predefined Benchmark Dose Response (BMRr) = 10% (3, 4, 5 parameter logistic model & 2, 3 parameter log-logistic model);
 - c. AIC for model selection;
 - d. Output: $\log(\text{Response (i.e. intensity)}|_{\text{material, gene}}) = \log(f(\text{dose}(\mu\text{g}/\text{mouse})|_{\text{model parameters}}) + \epsilon$
 - e. **Functional Pathway Analysis** using only the genes that have available BMD values: included pathways with at least 5 affected genes/probes for GO and KEGG

ontologies, 4 for Wikipathways database (due to very small gene counts per pathway):

- i. Fisher's exact test was implemented to identify statistically significant ontology terms and Benjamini & Hochberg (BH) method was used for multiple testing correction of the Fisher's exact p-values;
 - ii. Statistical significance threshold on (BH) adjusted p-values = 0.05.
- f. Median BMDt was used to represent the gene set or pathway BMDt.

C. AOP-independent and AOP-dependent BMD analysis and grouping:

4 approaches for Median pathway BMD, for each specific ontology are available:

1. only the pathway with the lowest Transcriptional Benchmark Dose (BMDt), namely the $BMD_{t_{\text{pathway, material}}}$ estimate, for each specific ontology/database;
2. Medians of all perturbed pathways, for which $BMD_{t_{\text{pathway, material}}}$ could be estimated, for each specific ontology/database;
3. Medians of the 10 pathways that were most significant indicated by the EnrichR combined score and common to all ENMs groups, for each specific ontology/database;
4. Medians of the KEGG Pathways that have been associated with a **specific Adverse Outcome** retrieved from the Comparative Toxicogenomics Database (**CTD**).

WORKFLOW Output:

$BMD_{\text{gene|ENM, pathway}}$, $BMD_{\text{ENM, most sensitive pathway}}$, $BMD_{\text{ENM, all pathways}}$, $BMD_{\text{ENM, top 10 pathways}}$, $BMD_{\text{ENM, AOP}}$

RANKING: using for each ENM type the $BMD_{\text{ENM, most sensitive pathway}}$ OR median $BMD_{\text{ENM, top 10 pathways}}$ OR median $BMD_{\text{ENM, AOP}}$

GROUPING: Identification of ENM classes based on their potency to affect critical biological pathways and their physicochemical properties, using **medians of $BMD_{\text{ENM, all pathways}}$** .

Case Study

Inhalation is reported as the most common and extensively investigated route of exposure to ENMs (Borm *et al.*, 2006). A significant fraction of the inhaled ENMs can reach distal regions in the lungs, that are more susceptible to the effects of the exposure since they lack the protective mucus present in the bronchial tree. Importantly, the alveolar ENM dose increases with exposure levels and persists for an extended period of time, even after ENM exposure has ceased, causing long-term damage to the lung cells (Kreyling, 2013).

The particle size is a critical parameter that affects the depth inside the lungs that ENMs can be found and is also associated with the ENMs mass-specific surface area, which has been identified as one of the most important factors that contribute to ENMs acute and chronic toxicity (Schmid & Stoeger,

2016). Upon inhalation, most ENMs induce dose-dependent increase in the levels of pro-inflammatory mediators (cytokines, chemokines, growth factors), acute phase response proteins, and influx of pro-inflammatory cells in the lung lining fluid (bronchoalveolar lavage fluid) resulting in lung inflammation (Saber *et al.*, 2013). The latter is associated with lung fibrosis, a pathological condition that has been reported as a result of ENM exposure in mice. Other, less frequent outcomes that have been reported are genotoxicity, carcinogenicity, and mesothelioma.

In this case study, global gene expression patterns from mice, that followed shortly after lung exposure to a set of ENMs with different properties, were extracted. TiO₂ ENMs were chosen, because they are classified as possibly carcinogenic to humans, in 'IARC monographs on the evaluation of carcinogenic risks to humans: carbon black, titanium dioxide, and talc, 2010.' The main question that was chosen to be answered by this case study is whether the short-term toxicogenomic profiles that are caused by the intratracheal exposure of mice to a variety of TiO₂ ENMs can be used to extract BMD values at gene or pathway level to successfully rank and/or group these ENMs by their potency to induce *in vivo* acute lung inflammation. Lung inflammation is a short-term local tissue response, which leads to the chronic medical condition of pulmonary fibrosis. The molecular events that eventually lead to the pathological phenotypes are described by AOP 173, "**Substance interaction with the resident lung cell membrane components leading to lung fibrosis**" [<https://aopwiki.org/aops/173>] (Figure 22).

Figure 22 : AOP 173 - Substance interaction with the resident lung cell membrane components leading to lung fibrosis.

A literature search was initially performed to collect available datasets and studies that aimed to investigate the transcriptional pulmonary responses to exposure to multiple doses of TiO₂ ENMs shortly after the exposure, i.e. 24h post-exposure timepoint. In order to minimize the sources of information loss, such as cross-species genetic differences or sex-dependent biological response, a set of restrictions was adopted. Thus, data corresponding to lung tissue samples from C57BL/6 mice and specifically only samples taken from animals of the same sex (female) analyzed using the Agilent Whole Genome microarray platform were used. The normalized and log₂ transformed gene expression values, as well as the corresponding phenotypic and exposure information, were retrieved from the [GEO database](#), a public repository that archives and freely distributes a great amount of microarray, next-generation sequencing, and other forms of high-throughput functional genomic data (Edgar *et al.*, 2002, Barrett *et al.*, 2013).

Apart from the data storage, GEO offers a collection of web-based interfaces and applications that facilitate querying and downloading the stored studies and gene expression patterns. Easy querying from a script is supported using the GEOquery R/Bioconductor library (Davis & Meltzer, 2007). GSE81570 dataset was downloaded using getGEO function. This object contains the respective series matrix that store the log₂ transformed and Locally WEighted Scatterplot Smoothing (LOWESS) normalized gene expression values, as well as the relevant information about all the samples that were analyzed and the experimental procedures utilised (Yang *et al.*, 2002).

The complete dataset consists of 233 samples that were extracted from female, 5–7 weeks old C57BL/6 mice, exposed to **6 TiO₂ ENMs** with varying properties:

- crystalline structure: anatase, rutile or anatase/rutile
- anatase ENM sizes: 8, 20 and 300 nm
- rutile ENMs surface modifications: hydrophobic or hydrophilic.

Control mice were only exposed to the vehicle, thus received 40 µL of MilliQ water, while the ENM-exposed mice received 54, 162 or 486 µg/mouse doses of individual ENMs via a single intratracheal instillation. More details about the ENM characterization and the experimental procedure are provided in Rahman *et al.* (2017). The preprocessing methodology is described in Nikota *et al.* (2016). Following removal of the data that correspond to other timepoints and samples that lacked exposure information, 115 samples remained for the downstream analysis, and their distribution into exposure categories is presented in Table 7. The phenotypic data for the first 20 samples included in the analysis are presented in Table 8. The **Dose µg/mouse** column and the **ENM details (type, size(in nm))** column are included in the linear modelling as independent variables, as described below. Table 9 contains the **LOWESS normalized, log₂ transformed intensities** for the first 10 samples included in the analysis. These measurements are the dependent variable in the linear model.

Table 7 : Exposure population data (only about the ENMs that were included in the downstream analysis).

ENM	Nanoparticle size (nm)	Dose ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mouse}$)	Number of Samples
Anatase	8	0	5
		54	5
		162	5
		486	5
	20	0	4
		54	5
		162	5
		486	4
	300	0	5
		54	5
		162	5
		486	5
Mixed rutile/anatase	20	0	5
		54	5
		162	5
		486	5
Rutile hydrophilic	20	0	4
		54	5
		162	5
		486	5
Rutile hydrophobic	20	0	4
		54	5
		162	4
		486	5

Table 8. Phenotypic data for the first 20 samples included in the analysis. ENMs doses range from 0 µg/mouse for control samples, corresponding to a 'negative' dose, and 54 µg/mouse corresponding to a 'middle' dose, 162 µg/mouse corresponding to a 'high' dose, and 486 µg/mouse corresponding to a 'very_high' dose for the animals exposed to ENMs via a single intratracheal instillation.

SampleID	Dose category	Dose (µg/mouse)	ENM details (type, size(in nm))
GSM2157260	negative	0	(Control sample)
GSM2157261	middle	54	Anatase, 20
GSM2157262	high	162	Anatase, 20
GSM2157263	very_high	486	Anatase, 20
GSM2157267	very_high	486	Anatase, 20
GSM2157268	high	162	Anatase, 20
GSM2157269	middle	54	Anatase, 20
GSM2157270	negative	0	(Control sample)
GSM2157275	negative	0	(Control sample)
GSM2157276	middle	54	Anatase, 20
GSM2157277	high	162	Anatase, 20
GSM2157282	negative	0	(Control sample)
GSM2157283	very_high	486	Anatase, 20
GSM2157284	middle	54	Anatase, 20
GSM2157285	high	162	Anatase, 20
GSM2157290	high	162	Anatase, 20
GSM2157291	middle	54	Anatase, 20
GSM2157292	very_high	486	Anatase, 20
GSM2157297	middle	54	Rutile - hydrophilic, 20
GSM2157298	negative	0	(Control sample)

Table 9. Normalized log2 transformed intensities (for the first 10 samples)

ProbeID	GSM2157260	GSM2157261	GSM2157262	GSM2157263	GSM2157267	GSM2157268	GSM2157269	GSM2157270	GSM2157275	GSM2157276
A_51_P100021	0.029862525	-0.028325985	-0.005386312	-0.12772028	-0.23467971	-0.222777421	-0.121399017	-0.017369259	-0.006185555	-0.12677288
A_51_P100034	0.56587875	0.365373361	0.441949109	0.932538644	0.944475702	0.889049183	1.147566574	0.842718637	0.552936122	0.666371921
A_51_P100052	-0.143794802	-0.144276397	0.052947706	0.021560375	0.133599593	-0.065231543	-0.14235927	-0.05498589	-0.185193805	-0.289641156
A_51_P100063	0.992853322	0.812133294	0.757421914	0.714684217	1.15085269	1.61835841	0.907339184	1.083142091	1.286500258	1.125569363
A_51_P100084	0.204706629	-0.203780375	0.223592674	0.203276797	0.431406159	-0.074038591	0.283050443	0.372942916	0.700752925	0.64327065
A_51_P100099	-0.35794919	0.039195371	-0.326068925	-0.363830538	-0.588631447	-0.461972965	-0.393207897	-0.645789716	-0.490741483	-0.39924524
A_51_P100155	-0.505203961	-0.443947587	-0.407879496	-0.335136964	-0.353840162	-0.339089185	-0.392036948	-0.450434255	-0.711456019	-0.582087726
A_51_P100174	-0.524461912	-0.482315368	0.016317949	-0.516455578	0.121645383	0.235901272	-0.201225783	-0.154454727	0.444804929	0.344625701
A_51_P100181	-0.239489666	-0.153954169	-0.376946222	-0.000146521	-0.14267918	0.038655357	0.048688673	-0.005411686	-0.420506901	-0.63099795
A_51_P100218	0.142534656	0.138327105	-0.110055878	-0.074413341	0.095902221	0.15801654	-0.090275628	0.059964229	-0.070322389	0.022059061
A_51_P100227	-1.660637029	-1.712244881	-0.791952208	-1.62311488	-1.710410612	-1.689721377	-1.126794825	-1.250993709	-1.352522621	-1.438418128
A_51_P100238	-0.019028984	-0.139422683	-0.002379886	-0.007739999	-0.088999459	-0.083705451	0.054468045	-0.073155793	0.16667919	0.078221101
A_51_P100246	-0.468215574	-0.559547065	-0.43651828	-0.019439661	-0.953671795	-0.969240276	-0.36582067	-0.654127733	-1.054763505	-1.036857732
A_51_P100289	0.164925864	0.181261719	-0.120088622	0.267852168	0.531130417	0.481262688	0.204296046	0.273430289	0.347785262	0.284309002
A_51_P100298	0.448485053	0.507155114	0.261992965	0.705507818	0.525607904	0.54942451	0.63844137	0.740367894	0.212157225	0.411054454
A_51_P100309	0.040025186	0.086122326	-0.130569919	0.023394068	-0.038428251	0.155544038	0.159796449	0.015403535	-0.012320151	-0.13310359
A_51_P100327	0.000766082	0.257920859	0.226554453	-0.150214799	-0.328864162	0.158059469	-0.260023158	-0.105715763	0.103460223	-0.1508832
A_51_P100347	-0.343633844	-0.385375311	-0.23314758	-0.118447989	-0.113901649	-0.269488039	-0.23728848	-0.196021454	-0.483440035	-0.393847921
A_51_P100379	0.04969412	0.050466582	0.075097864	0.169511267	-0.118625044	0.054906334	0.043277046	0.042075225	0.069743274	0.075439393
A_51_P100428	-0.117112598	-0.096537885	-0.01905053	-0.024128739	-0.078316017	-0.133786924	0.06846041	0.031303207	0.069540563	0.166516341

The 'limma' R/Bioconductor package was chosen to perform the linear modeling (Ritchie *et al.*, 2015). The linear model that was used is:

$$Y_i \sim a + b_1 X_i + b_2 D_i$$

where

Y_i : is the measurement, here the normalized, log2 transformed intensity for gene i

a : is the intercept of the model

X_i : is the exposure of interest

D_i : is the respective dose of the exposure of interest.

D6.2 AOP-based grouping of ENMs

The moderated t-statistic was used to test the exposure effects compared to the control and the negative control samples and FDR for multiple testing correction (Benjamini *et al.*, 1995). The moderated t-statistic differs from the ordinary t-statistic in that the SEs have been moderated across genes, i.e., shrunk towards a common value, using a simple Bayesian model (Smyth, 2004). Genes showing expression changes of at least 0.5-fold in either direction and FDR corrected p-values smaller than 0.05 were considered as significantly differentially expressed genes (DEGs) and used in the downstream analyses (Table 10).

Table 10: The annotated gene list for the 15 first results from limma linear modelling results for anatase, 8 nm exposure.

ProbelD	logFC	AveExpr	t	P.Value	adj.P.Val	B	ENSEMBL	ENTREZID	GENENAME	SYMBOL
A_51_P100856	-0.855461662	-2.163500297	-5.12380918	1.28E-06	0.000188107	5.152429626	ENSMUSG00000026193	14268	fibronectin 1	Fn1
A_51_P107321	-0.572268819	-1.671441361	-5.139485701	1.20E-06	0.000187074	5.214939493	ENSMUSG00000022186	67041	3-oxoacid CoA transferase 1	Oxct1
A_51_P108226	0.775183027	2.629422613	4.192755374	5.58E-05	0.001587028	1.663355384	ENSMUSG00000051748	66107	WAP four-disulfide core domain 21	Wfdc21
A_51_P111462	0.560044241	0.65135011	3.940305728	0.000142961	0.002827057	0.801354765	ENSMUSG00000042348	218639	ADP-ribosylation factor-like 15	Arl15
A_51_P112966	0.830039632	2.316764703	4.207824637	5.27E-05	0.001530925	1.716029727	ENSMUSG00000050370	12642	cholesterol 25-hydroxylase	Ch25h
A_51_P113399	-0.548723922	-0.800690655	-4.594493128	1.16E-05	0.000601541	3.11225963	ENSMUSG00000116207	18115	nicotinamide nucleotide transhydrogenase	Nnt
A_51_P113399	-0.548723922	-0.800690655	-4.594493128	1.16E-05	0.000601541	3.11225963	ENSMUSG00000025453	18115	nicotinamide nucleotide transhydrogenase	Nnt
A_51_P113784	-0.616039997	-2.571737193	-2.803074766	5.98E-03	0.033746873	-2.552986955	ENSMUSG00000024735	28000	pre-mRNA processing factor 19	Prpf19
A_51_P114462	1.05632183	2.213159359	5.047215316	1.78E-06	0.000220147	4.848666177	ENSMUSG00000031780	20295	chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 17	Ccl17
A_51_P115334	-0.558991965	-0.228803378	-4.331586976	3.27E-05	0.001131323	2.153681152	ENSMUSG00000014867	20932	surfeit gene 4	Surf4
A_51_P118415	-0.545624697	-1.816670899	-4.673552157	8.41E-06	0.000492101	3.407904456	ENSMUSG00000000278	74617	serine carboxypeptidase 1	Scpep1
A_51_P120295	1.046636572	0.241106843	6.247420195	7.99E-09	9.56E-06	9.890871123	ENSMUSG00000022445	76279	cytochrome P450, family 2, subfamily d, polypeptide 26	Cyp2d26
A_51_P124505	-0.543236542	-1.474667128	-4.489512684	1.76E-05	0.000766967	2.724889952	ENSMUSG00000037851	105148	isoleucine-tRNA synthetase	lars
A_51_P125535	-0.634372502	0.422495473	-4.831085062	4.40E-06	0.000350013	4.006760535	ENSMUSG00000009630	19053	protein phosphatase 2 (formerly 2A), catalytic subunit, beta isoform	Ppp2cb
A_51_P131561	0.596751884	5.403822883	3.020457339	3.14E-03	2.17E-02	-1.983932941	ENSMUSG00000032068	76509	placenta expressed transcript 1	Plet1
A_51_P136288	0.528348491	2.59809515	3.217923827	0.001694862	0.014609538	-1.43617696	ENSMUSG00000056290	60361	membrane-spanning 4-domains, subfamily A, member 4B	Ms4a4b
A_51_P136289	0.512599449	2.572743868	3.189201263	0.001856663	0.015432839	-1.517635807	ENSMUSG00000056290	60361	membrane-spanning 4-domains, subfamily A, member 4B	Ms4a4b
A_51_P136820	-0.621958723	-0.693666777	-3.497582212	0.000677463	0.00795483	-0.612186755	ENSMUSG0000004207	19156	prosaposin	Psap
A_51_P140311	-0.654500797	-0.515940608	-4.763465092	5.82E-06	0.000401022	3.748137982	ENSMUSG00000029713	14693	guanine nucleotide binding protein (G protein), beta 2	Gnb2
A_51_P140803	0.576154455	0.464143929	4.497669526	1.70E-05	0.000749321	2.754771892	ENSMUSG00000030236	28253	solute carrier organic anion transporter family, member 1b2	Slco1b2

The next step was the application of Functional Pathway Analysis (commonly called Gene Set Enrichment Analysis) (Subramanian *et al.*, 2005), using the 'enrichR' R/Cran package (Chen *et al.*, 2013, Kuleshov *et al.*, 2016). The DEGs list was used as input and the results were lists of significantly altered ('biological process') GO terms (Ashburner *et al.*, 2000), mouse KEGG pathways (Kanehisa *et al.*, 2016) and mouse Wikipathways (Kelder *et al.*, 2012, Martens *et al.*, 2018, Pico *et al.*, 2008).

For the pathway BMD response modelling, the normalized gene expression data were analyzed using 'bmd' and 'drc' R libraries (Ritz and Streibig, 2005, Ritz *et al.*, 2015). An R script was developed in order to calculate the median pathway BMD associated with the perturbed gene sets extracted in the previous part of the analysis as well as the set of pathways that were retrieved using 'enrichR'. Then the normalized log2 intensities were filtered and centered using the mean of the respective control sample values and three, four and five parameter logistic and two and three-parameter log-logistic models were fitted to the data using the BMD function of the 'bmd' R/Cran library, setting the

Benchmark Response level at 10%. The Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) was used for model selection and the model with the lowest AIC for every model type was used to select the best final model. Afterwards, the probes for which BMD values were successfully calculated, and were lower than the highest dose were then mapped using 'enrichR' to GO, KEGG and Wikipathways ontologies. Functional Pathway Analysis outputs, which are sets of significantly enriched terms from which only the terms associated with five or more genes/transcripts were collected, and matched to the respective median BMD.

The KEGG pathways that have been associated with the specific AOP (Lung Fibrosis - AOP 173) were retrieved from CTD using the 'CTDquerier' R/Bioconductor package (Davis *et al.*, 2019, Hernandez-Ferrer & Gonzalez, 2018) and the term '**Pulmonary Fibrosis**' (MESH:D011658) in the query. Table 11 presents the filtered results for the AOP 173 related KEGG pathways that were found to be altered by the exposure to ENMs in our analysis. For the DEGs that take part in these pathways, the respective BMDL was collected, if it is available, and the median BMDL value for each pathway was then calculated (Table 12). These median pathway BMDL values were then used to group the ENMs according to their potential to cause biological events that will lead to the manifestation of lung fibrosis in the future.

Table 11: The AOP 173 (Pulmonary Fibrosis, MESH:D011658) associated enriched KEGG pathways that are statistically significantly perturbed (Adjusted p-value < 0.05) due to the ENM exposure and that include more than 5 differentially expressed genes.

Lung fibrosis associated KEGG pathways	Overlap	P.value	Adjusted. P.value	Odds.Ratio	Combined. Score	Genes	Genes count
Rap1 signaling pathway	5/209	0.0552313	0.2656361	2.4411679	7.0701737	VASP;ITGB1;GNAS;PIK3R1;ACTG1	5
Transcriptional misregulation in cancer	5/183	0.0344343	0.1968605	2.7880004	9.3919398	CSF2;NCOR1;BCL2A1C;TCF3;BCL2A1B	5
PI3K-Akt signaling pathway	9/357	0.0088293	0.0743131	2.5724576	12.1669066	ITGB1;PPP2CB;HSP90AB1;CDC37;FN1;PPP2R2A;PIK3R1;EIF4B;TLR2	9
Hepatitis C	5/160	0.0208315	0.1402651	3.1887755	12.3446793	CLDN10;PPP2CB;CASP8;PPP2R2A;PIK3R1	5
Focal adhesion	6/199	0.0138391	0.0998393	3.0766075	13.1686695	VASP;ITGB1;FN1;PIK3R1;VCL;ACTG1	6
Endocytosis	8/269	0.0051572	0.0504075	3.0346711	15.9847079	ARF3;H2-T22;NEDD4;H2-K1;H2-Q2;H2-Q1;H2-Q10;ARFGAP2	8
Hepatitis B	6/163	0.0054716	0.0518091	3.7561037	19.5624900	SMAD4;CASP8;TAB2;PIK3R1;D1PAS1;TLR2	6
Natural killer cell mediated cytotoxicity	5/118	0.0061547	0.0548490	4.3237634	22.0103024	CSF2;TYROBP;H2-K1;PIK3R1;HCST	5

D6.2 AOP-based grouping of ENMs

Regulation of actin cytoskeleton	8/217	0.0013832	0.0161201	3.7618734	24.7656331	ITGB1;GNA13;FN1;IQGAP1;PIK3R1;WASF1;VCL;ACTG1	8
Apoptosis	6/141	0.0026936	0.0272054	4.3421624	25.6920396	CASP8;AIFM1;BCL2A1C;PIK3R1;BCL2A1B;ACTG1	6
Proteoglycans in cancer	8/203	0.0009025	0.0124300	4.0213130	28.1907355	ITGB1;CTTN;FN1;IQGAP1;PIK3R1;EIF4B;TLR2;ACTG1	8
Viral carcinogenesis	9/229	0.0004438	0.0074703	4.0103378	30.9605150	H2-T22;CASP8;H2-K1;H2-Q2;PIK3R1;D1PAS1;HIST1H2BA;H2-Q1;H2-Q10	9
IL-17 signaling pathway	5/91	0.0020208	0.0218682	5.6066383	34.7849811	CSF2;HSP90AB1;CASP8;TAB2;CCL17	5
Leukocyte transendothelial migration	6/115	0.0009531	0.0125562	5.3238687	37.0316425	VASP;ITGB1;CLDN10;PIK3R1;VCL;ACTG1	6
Hippo signaling pathway	8/159	0.0001770	0.0044684	5.1341291	44.3565790	MOB1A;PPP2CB;SMAD4;WWC1;TCF7;PPP2R2A;AFP;ACTG1	8
Chagas disease (American trypanosomiasis)	6/103	0.0005335	0.0085081	5.9441252	44.7951193	PPP2CB;CASP8;GNAS;PPP2R2A;PIK3R1;TLR2	6
Autoimmune thyroid disease	5/78	0.0010161	0.0128283	6.5410780	45.0796734	H2-T22;H2-K1;H2-Q2;H2-Q1;H2-Q10	5
Platelet activation	7/125	0.0002346	0.0050784	5.7142857	47.7567987	VASP;ITGB1;FGB;GNA13;GNAS;PIK3R1;ACTG1	7
Acute myeloid leukemia	5/69	0.0005807	0.0087975	7.3942621	55.0968129	CSF2;TCF7;BCL2A1C;PIK3R1;BCL2A1B	5
Graft-versus-host disease	5/64	0.0004098	0.0073044	7.9719388	62.1795325	H2-T22;H2-K1;H2-Q2;H2-Q1;H2-Q10	5
Amoebiasis	7/106	0.0000838	0.0025399	6.7385445	63.2531989	CSF2;ARG1;FN1;GNAS;PIK3R1;VCL;TLR2	7
Allograft rejection	5/63	0.0003808	0.0072113	8.0984775	63.7613136	H2-T22;H2-K1;H2-Q2;H2-Q1;H2-Q10	5
Adherens junction	6/72	0.0000749	0.0025217	8.5034014	80.7765865	SMAD4;TCF7;IQGAP1;WASF1;VCL;ACTG1	6
Antigen processing and presentation	7/90	0.0000293	0.0012690	7.9365079	82.8361159	H2-T22;HSP90AB1;H2-K1;H2-Q2;H2-Q1;H2-Q10;TAPBP	7
Type I diabetes mellitus	6/69	0.0000589	0.0022303	8.8731145	86.4234693	H2-T22;H2-K1;CPE;H2-Q2;H2-Q1;H2-Q10	6
Bacterial invasion of epithelial cells	7/74	0.0000081	0.0006103	9.6525097	113.2138164	ITGB1;CTTN;FN1;PIK3R1;WASF1;VCL;ACTG1	7
Viral myocarditis	9/87	0.0000002	0.0000279	10.5559465	163.7017940	H2-T22;CASP8;H2-K1;DAG1;H2-Q2;H2-Q1;EIF4G3;H2-Q10;ACTG1	9

Table 12: Median Log BMDL_t values for the AOP173 (Pulmonary Fibrosis, MESH:D011658) associated KEGG pathways for the ENMs under study

Lung fibrosis associated KEGG pathways	Median log(BMDL _t pathway, material)					
	Anatase, 8nm	Anatase, 20nm	Anatase, 300nm	Mixed Anatase/Rutile, 20nm	Rutile, hydrophilic, 20nm	Rutile hydrophobic, 20nm
Rap1 signaling pathway	-549.92	-8.55	-110.68	-106.61	-261.17	-282.63
Transcriptional misregulation in cancer	-240.70	-322.12	-314.89	-240.70	-211.72	-325.16
PI3K-Akt signaling pathway	-214.65	-177.24	-116.27	-228.01	-406.57	-549.92
Hepatitis C	-14.18	-406.57	-218.06	-406.57	-21.04	-376.35
Focal adhesion	-376.35	-314.89	-397.61	-5153.68	-1854.79	-1914.02
Endocytosis	-14787.99	-682.72	-2819.64	-10044.30	-21997.45	-21092.88
Hepatitis B	-14787.99	-3776.75	-6431.97	-7393.99	-522.62	-5499.58
Natural killer cell mediated cytotoxicity	-14787.99	-1837.95	-1525.94	-5499.58	-1837.95	-13110.04
Regulation of actin cytoskeleton	-1837.95	-5499.58	-1018.94	-1837.95	-23253.10	-1837.95
Apoptosis	-2855.82	-28521.81	-765.91	-1810.86	-1665.49	-4618.16
Proteoglycans in cancer	-721.85	-3378.37	-2058.00	-1788.84	-2058.00	-2855.82
Viral carcinogenesis	-721.85	-2855.82	-10827.48	-1810.86	-25309.49	-2260.66
IL-17 signaling pathway	-20889.05	-25309.49	-3827.08	-25309.50	-3466.46	-13317.14
Leukocyte transendothelial migration	-13317.14	-3161.14	-13317.14	-8956.85	-13816.12	-57.54
Hippo signaling pathway	-57.54	-19741.21	-4480.96	-33184.80	-2438.03	-21637.29
Chagas disease (American trypanosomiasis)	-121.73	-251.55	-1355.29	-773.54	-21637.29	-20232.07
Autoimmune thyroid disease	-23.30	-918.81	-8956.85	-13816.10	-918.81	-34.34
Platelet activation	-918.81	-86132.38	-0.01	-3641.00	-21637.29	-8043.11
Acute myeloid leukemia	-5496.90	-934.02	-1919.63	0.00	-57914.23	-26.24
Graft-versus-host disease	0.00	-514.10	-1791.67	-199.25	-48114.91	-26.24
Amoebiasis	-361.62	0.00	-956.04	-3306.64	-26.24	-5496.89
Allograft rejection	-666.26	-26.24	-1919.63	-26.24	-1791.67	-22.15

D6.2 AOP-based grouping of ENMs

Adherens junction	-446.30	-48050.93	-26.24	-3.86	-689.13	-86.18
Antigen processing & presentation	-124.64	-12.44	-107.87	-300.11	-73.60	-72.31
Type I diabetes mellitus	-93.57	-12.44	-116.06	-124.39	-27.96	-475.59
Bacterial invasion of epithelial cells	-124.64	-116.06	0.47	-406.88	-116.06	-7.69
Viral myocarditis	-116.06	-254.28	-116.06	-115.61	-30.08	-100.60

The analysis proceeded with the application of the four different strategies for ranking and grouping based on the BMD results, as listed in the Workflow Description section. Hierarchical clustering was used to group the BMDL values corresponding to the exposure to the 6 ENMs, using many available distance measures ("euclidean", "maximum", "manhattan", "canberra", or "minkowski") and agglomeration methods ("ward", "single", "complete", "average", "mcquitty", "median" or "centroid"). ENM grouping, after applying hierarchical clustering using the Euclidean distance and the average agglomeration method, is shown in Figure 23.

The complete workflow has been implemented in an R script which is available at the following link: https://github.com/NanoCommons/Code-and-workflows/tree/master/AOP_NM_Grouping.

Figure 23: ENM grouping after applying hierarchical clustering (distance:Euclidean, agglomeration: average) on BMD Medians of the KEGG Pathways that have been associated with AOP-173.

Conclusions

In the context of the NanoCommons project, a number of novel grouping/read across approaches and tools have been developed that facilitate the process of searching for similar ENMs, defining groups with similar toxicity behaviour and eventually computing the read-across predictions. Particular emphasis was given on employing computational nanoinformatics tools for automating, optimising and speeding up the complete process to the greatest possible extent. The tools range from defining similarity scores to the utilisation of machine learning technologies and algorithms like kNN and random forest.

A truly innovative development was the application of mathematical programming algorithms for adding mathematical rigor to the definition of the grouping/read-across problem and for obtaining optimal solutions regarding the selection of important variables, defining the grouping boundaries and computing the read-across predictions. Many of the grouping/read across methods integrated into the NanoCommons infrastructure to date are considering the concept of biological similarity and AOPs in addition to the simpler considerations of ENM physico-chemical property similarities. This is achieved by defining separately the biological similarity and making it a prerequisite for considering ENMs as similar, by developing read-across models that predict MIEs in AOPs and by applying the BMD approach on differentially expressed genes and combining the results to the level of pathways and AOPs.

Grouping/read-across approaches constitute one key component of the complete risk assessment workflow presented in Deliverable 6.1. Next steps in the development of the NanoCommons e-infrastructure for AOP modelling and ENMs grouping and read-across is the inclusion of these methods into the overall risk assessment process and the integration with other computational methods such as external exposure models and biokinetics models which will facilitate the achievement of risk assessment at the AOP level. Additionally, further extensions of the grouping/read-across methods and ideas will address read-across case studies where the end-points to be predicted are classes or categorical variables.

Abbreviations

AIC - Akaike Information Criterion
AO - Adverse Outcome
AOP - Adverse Outcome Pathway
AOP-KB - AOP Knowledge Base
BH - Benjamini & Hochberg
BMD - Benchmark Dose
BMDL - Benchmark Dose Lower
BMDt - Transcriptional Benchmark Dose
BMDU - Benchmark Dose Upper
BMRr - Benchmark Dose Response
CTD - Comparative Toxicogenomics Database
CNT - Carbon Nanotubes
CPH - L-hydroxy-3-carboxy-2, 2, 5, 5-tetramethylpyrrolidine
DEG- Differentially Expressed Gene
DMPO - 5,5-dimethyl-1-pyrroline-N-oxide
ECHA - European Chemicals Agency
EFSA - European Food Safety Authority
ENM - Engineered Nanomaterial
ESR - Electron Spin Resonance
FC- Fold Change
FDR - False Discovery Rate
FLSV - Final Safety Limit Value
GA - Genetic Algorithm
GEO - Gene Expression Omnibus
GO - Gene Ontology
GSVA - Gene Set Variation Analysis
GUI - Graphical User Interface
HCAII - Carbonic Anhydrase II
IATA - Integrated Approach to Testing and Assessment
JECFA - Joint FAO/WHO Expert Committee on Food Additives

KE- Key Event

KEGG - Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes

kNN - k Nearest Neighbours

LOAEL - Lowest Observed Adverse Effect Level

LOWESS - Locally WEighted Scatterplot Smoothing

MDA- Mean Decrease of Accuracy

MIE - Molecular Initiating Events

MILP - Mixed Integer Linear Programming

MINLP - Mixed Integer NonLinear Programming

MOE - Margin of Exposure

MSE - Mean Squared Error

MWCNT - Multi-Walled Carbon NanoTubes

NOAEL - No Observed Adverse Effect Level

NF - Nanofibers

OECD - Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

OPLRA - Optimal Piecewise Linear Regression Algorithm

PCF - Protein Corona Fingerprints

QMRF - QSAR Model Reporting Form

QNAR - Quantitative Nanostructure-Activity Relationship

QPRF - QSAR Predictive Model Form

QRA - Quantitative Read-Across

QSAR - Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship

PLA - Piecewise Linear Optimization

POD - Point of Departure

RAAF - Read-Across Assessment Framework

RAV - read-across value (predicted)

RF - Random Forest

RFE - Recursive Feature Elimination

RP - Reference Point

STIS - short-term inhalation studies

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